

EOSC-Life Sustainability paper

Rolling notes & supplementary material (SP#)

“Be Sustainable”, Recommendations for FAIR Resources in Life Sciences research: EOSC-Life's Lessons” in EMBO Journal

Connection details

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81867144296?pwd=WjN4VytVanpRRW9lYkxoRUNuaEVIQT09>

ID recurrent meeting: 818 6714 4296

Code secret : 877000

Meeting Rolling notes

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit?usp=sharing

Usual time

Friday at 13:00 PM

mailto: ERASED FOR ZENODO

Authors, affiliations & ORCIDs: (please add yourself, will be re-ordonate taking in account participation)

Validated format

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LINK TO THE EMBOJ VERSION

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bO2dzUSf05_R_sCnIRkoWhKrFDtf_YtTuTr5Ki5sivE/e/dit?usp=sharing

PAPER DRAFT (FROZEN)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Uz11TG43gyEzdGO1MYQ6U3GP-rxtmulfQU7maWAJ/CRA/edit?usp=sharing>

FROZEN:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPy-Glt1BJjhNM0-xKTnzCICQ5OFT077IhyeGkPc/edit?usp=sharing>

PAPER WORK MANAGEMENT:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit?usp=sharing>

FIGURE DRAFTS

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1wXErGWUVtsXUS8bCtmgPAvJmBZQyU92MlqfbRqHcScc/edit#slide=id.g210cc4c1b03_0_25

IMAGES FROM EOSC-LIFE WEBSITE FOR CREATING FIGURES:

Folder link:

WORLD CAFE SUSTAINABILITY overview

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Nycpz0wWDDjeWI6_NjMwIGKAehrqAZ9X/edit#gid=1077729791

Shorthand (tool for complex representation)

<https://shorthand.com/featured/animation-effects/index.html>

PAPER DRAFT (FROZEN)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPY-GIt1BJhNM0-xKTNzCICQ5OFT077IhyeGkPc/edit?usp=sharing>

FOLDER WITH ALL DOCUMENTS:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1WTYdGtrmuVQfaJ529iZdjAHaP5IucvAA>

Meeting SP#xx xx/07/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Template

Agenda

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Notes & Actions to be done

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Author Query Form EMBOJ EOSC-Life sent 03/11/2023

Journal: EMBJ Article: 2023115008 Dear Author, During the copyediting of your manuscript the following queries arose. Please refer to the query reference callout numbers in the page proofs and respond to each by marking the necessary comments using the PDF annotation tools. Please remember illegible or unclear comments and corrections may delay publication. Many thanks for your assistance.

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AUTHORS RESPONSE: We have built a synopsis image (AR)

@all please validate slide 2

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jtO44NTaCZ9fhlvgpzhmMRmngBfhNXse/edit#slide=id.g294f1782d16_0_0

3 AUTHOR: As per journal style Keywords are not required, hence it has been deleted. Please check.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: Checked and OK

4 AUTHOR: Please check all website addresses and the functionality of the underlying links and confirm that they are correct. (Please note that it is the responsibility of the author(s) to ensure that all URLs given in this article are correct and usable.).

AUTHORS RESPONSE: Checked (JMB and RD checked all of them)

5 AUTHOR: Please check and confirm whether the bold formatting can be retained or removed throughout the article.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: Checked, all bold can be retained

6 AUTHOR: Please check and provide the suitable title for Figures 1–6.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: Title proposals (in commentary in the text)

Fig 1: Position and organisation of EOSC-Life in the EOSC and LS RIs ecosystems

Fig 2: EOSC-Life operational framework, extending from the end user to the EOSC ecosystem

Fig 3: EOSC-Life Sensitive Data toolbox development scheme

Fig 4: Key components driving, facilitating and challenging the sustainability process - lessons from the EOSC-Life project

Fig 5: EOSC-Life Recommendations for ensuring and facilitating sustainability

Fig 6: Cross-correlation between Be SUsustainable Recommendations and FAIR principles implementation

7 AUTHOR: Figure 6 caption and citation is present in this article but the image is not given. Please check and provide the figure 6 image.

Figure 6. FAIR x Be SURE "Be Sustainable REcommendations"		[R1]	[R2]	[R3]	[R4]	[R5]	[R6]	[R7]	[R8]	[R9]	[R10]	[R11]	[R12]
F	F1. Globally unique and persistent identifier	Orange	Teal	Orange	White	Orange	Teal	Orange	Orange	Orange	Teal	White	White
F	F2. Rich metadata	Orange	Teal	Orange	White	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
F	F3. Metadata include data identifier	Orange	Teal	White	White	Orange	Teal	Orange	White	White	White	White	White
F	F4. (Meta)data indexed	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	Teal	White	White	White
A	A1. Standardised communications protocol	Orange	Teal	White	White	Orange	Teal	Orange	Orange	Orange	Teal	Teal	White
A	A1.1 Protocol open, free, and universally implementable	Orange	Teal	White	White	Teal	Teal	Teal	Teal	Orange	Teal	Teal	White
A	A1.2 Authentication and authorisation procedure	Orange	Teal	White	White	Teal	Teal	Teal	Orange	White	Teal	Teal	White
A	A2. Metadata accessible, data no longer available	Orange	Teal	White	White	Orange	White	White	Orange	White	Teal	Teal	White
I	I1. (Meta)data language for knowledge representation	Orange	Teal	White	White	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
I	I2. FAIR (Meta)data vocabularies	Orange	Teal	Orange	White	White	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
I	I3. Qualified references to other (meta)data	Orange	Teal	White	White	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
R	R1. Plurality of accurate and relevant (Meta)data attributes	White	Teal	White	Orange	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
R	R1.1.(Meta)data for data usage license	White	Teal	White	White	Orange	White	Teal	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
R	R1.2. Provenance (Meta)data	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White
R	R1.3. Domain-relevant community standards for (Meta)data	Orange	Teal	White	Orange	Orange	White	Orange	Orange	Orange	White	White	White

[R1] Build with the experts	[R7] Curate NOW	Should help to follow the BeSuRe recommendation
[R2] Publish, communicate, disseminate	[R8] Establish federated governance	
[R3] Demonstrate, not only tell	[R9] Harmonise and integrate	
[R4] Plan training for acute and future needs	[R10] Reward sustainability	
[R5] Metadata makes FAIR	[R11] Be open AND be inclusive	
[R6] Be prepared, agile and act timely	[R12] Treat innovation and sustainability independently	

AUTHORS RESPONSE: Table 2 -> Figure 6 (Done by Romain) available here https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/17_rP_HiVBkEiCqWxfhDBIq_iz3Kr_NIQ/edit?usp=sharing&oid=116842745610159845034&rtopof=true&sd=true

8 AUTHOR: Please make sure that all deposited data are released upon publication of this article so that they are available to readers.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: 3 PDF to be posted on Zenodo, with emails erased

- rolling notes
- Figure Slides
- Paper Management Google sheet
- Zenodo DOI to be added in the paper

9 AUTHOR: Please confirm that the funding information includes all funders and grant numbers. Please check that the displayed funder names match the official FundRef Registry organisation names.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: we confirm, funders are also in acknowledgement part

10 AUTHOR: As per journal style Abbreviations list is not allowed, hence the section "Initials and acronyms" has been deleted. Please check.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: OK

11 AUTHOR: Reference "David et al, 2023b" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list.

AUTHORS RESPONSE: References to supplementary materials are moved into supplementary material, at the end (**To be done by Romain**)

12 AUTHOR: Reference "European Commission et al, 2021" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

13 AUTHOR: Reference "Harrison et al, 2021" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

14 AUTHOR: Reference "Knapp et al, 2016" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem (PG - please delete the reference from the reference list as related text was removed in an earlier version)**

15 AUTHOR: Please provide the "location of publisher" for reference Knapp et al., 2016. **PG - please delete the reference from the reference list as related text was removed in an earlier version)**

16 AUTHOR: Reference "Kolodkin et al, 2020" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

17 AUTHOR: Please check and provide the page ranges for reference Lawson et al., 2021.

18 AUTHOR: Reference "McGovern, 2018b" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

19 AUTHOR: Reference "Nurnberger, 2018" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

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21 AUTHOR: Please provide the "location of publisher" for reference Scott, 2017.

22 AUTHOR: Reference "Scott, 2019" is not cited in the text. Please indicate where it should be cited; or delete from the reference list. **AUTHORS RESP idem**

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26 AUTHOR: Please provide the "location of publisher" for reference Tamm & Luyet, 2010.

Meeting SP#36 30/10/2023 13:00 CEST

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82552317732?pwd=9QpVBCpSvFbbBwpDBoSMbjweEZPZJp.1>

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- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **J-M Burel (Dundee, Euro-Biolmaging)**
- **J-K Heriche (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, EMBL Heidelberg)**

- ... [add yours!]

Apologised:

- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**

Agenda

- *Payment done*
- *Proof validation Rq*
 - <https://articlereview.pubmate.in/#/?templateID=c838b025776a43af8ca661078a9a4379165538714>
 - *Possible Graphical abstract. Teaser made by Arina before here - please feel free to edit and take it as you see needed:*
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jtO44NTaCZ9fhlvgpzhmMRmngBfhNXse/edit#slide=id.p1>
 - *Author Query form content:*
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TLohJe2i6QC3yh7rdJ8325l2jcUgP7LR2nUqiJGLtRQ/edit?usp=sharing>

Actions

See the query form content

Other

Preprint <https://zenodo.org/records/8068648>

Poster 1: <https://zenodo.org/records/10018907>

Poster 2: <https://zenodo.org/records/10022317> (authors to be filled)

Meeting SP#35 18/08/2023 13:00 CEST

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- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)**
- **Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)**
- ... [add yours!]

Apologised:

- **Jean-Marie Burel**
-

Agenda

- *Submission information / next step*
- *Communication plan:*
 - *Complete the contact file with on the web published informations*
 - https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BAYPb_mjCq9K91iRMumWbaKmMFLdJlJqPDeJ8wALAAk/edit#gid=969377720

- *todo list* [Contact4dissemination_SP_RD7_23062023](#)
- *templates*
- *Communication agenda*

Notes & Actions to be done

- Updated version of D1.4 is here [EOSC_LIFE_D1_4_Draft_3_Shorter_Version - Google Docs](#)
- Idea: EOSC-Life related projects - activate contacts in these projects who might be willing to also support dissemination efforts (ISIDORe, BY-COVID, EOSC4Cancer, CanSERV, *other?* EOSC-Future, EOSC-Task Forces, EOSC Association,...Other EOSC Cluster projects?)
- Suggestion: Add link to paper to any social media posts that go out regarding EOSC-Life in the period from the publication of the paper until (tentative) end of December 2023 to continue to remind people of the paper.
- Suggestion: Promote paper at events that occur in Fall 2023 (*prepare list?*) or at any events / meetings where people will gather together.
- Prepare 1-2 posters for presentation at upcoming events in Fall 2023.
- *Editor response / submission*
 - *Dear Romain,*
 -
 - *Thank you for your message and indicating this. I am happy to hereby confirm receipt of your formal commentary manuscript submission in our online system.*
 - *We will contact you shortly regarding our editorial conclusion and next steps.*
 -
 - *Best regards,*
 - *Daniel*
- *Each partner / infrastructure: website / newsletter / contact for social media*
- *Email to each partner to be prepared?*
- *Tweet / linkedIn template -> Sara*
- *Video template: candidate for [transcript] 40s is optimal length (can also link to longer versions for more interested viewers)*
 - *Ideas:*
 - *Short MESSAGE/Recommendation NbX (5 s)*
 - *Short presentation of EOSC Life 2 sentences (10 s)*
 - *Short presentation of RI/partner (15 s)*
 - *MESSAGE Recommendation NbX (15 s)*
 - *Example application impact (10 s)*
 - *Paper teaser (5s)*
 - *Start and END: same typology of logo / page "BeSure recommendations"*
- *Agenda: **timeline** for dissemination milestones (over next year?) / other [light] preparation steps (august / september?)*

Sara I have created a folder called "Final Dissemination" in the EOSC-Life WP10 Google Drive folder where I will upload templates with EOSC-Life branding that can then be modified as needed. I will try to create templates that have formats appropriate for sharing via LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, etc. during this next week.

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TECwSq9KL6tWlw5iwzyeduTyGrZUjXvh?usp=sharing>

I have uploaded the "All-Hands" poster to the "Final Dissemination" folder (linked above). This can be modified as needed. QR codes should all still work. I have grouped some images, but it should be possible to upgroup them to work with them. If any of the original images are needed, please just let me know:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/17fYw4KL7HMAZftVHdS0M7GYUAB2CTAyH/edit?usp=sharing&oid=110252972012726017297&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Meeting SP#34 17/08/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)
- Jean-Marie Burel

Agenda

- FYI, reviewer note to editors
- D1.4 infos?
- Brainstorming Paper communication Plan
- (opening a shared doc to follow progresses)
- Contact list (need list for 13 RIs and 47 partners)
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BAYPb_mjCq9K91iRMumWbaKmMFLdJljQpDeJ8wALAAk/edit#gid=969377720
-

Notes & Actions to be done

- D1.4 infos
 - Phil to circulate tagged updated shorter version of D1.4 with actions for folk to update the text with "intros/teasers" to get readers to look at the published version
- reviewer note to editors:

It has been brought to my attention that some of the authors of this MS are participating in a research project that has just been granted and that also involves the following reviewers:

Giovanni Lamanna
Franciska de Jong

The project has not yet started. If, nevertheless, this is considered to be a conflict of interest, please let me know if you would like us to provide alternative names.

Sara volunteers to tackle these items in next two weeks:

- Compile comprehensive list of **dissemination channels** (websites, social media channels, other channels (Slack, etc.), blogs, official EU forums and/or newsletters) that will be used to disseminate the link to the EMBO paper once published AND **organisations** that will be requested to support dissemination efforts
- Compile list of appropriate **hashtags and handles** that will be used to reach specific stakeholder audiences/communities (see [Table 5 in 10.2](#))
- Create a **timeline** for dissemination milestones (over next year?) to be achieved
- Create **draft of a short article** to be sent to communication officers at organisations that will be requested to support dissemination efforts (can be adapted for release on their news channels)
- Create **draft press release** for ending of project, citing link to published paper if available - pending approval by PMs

Romain volunteers to tackle these items:

- Create a communication material file including
 - TODO List
 - How to do section for tweets, videos, linkedin, website links, slack channels, reddit accounts,
 - Social media Contacts (lead Sara) for media dissemination including Forums & newsletters (RDA, ESFRI, LSRI, EOSC...)
 - Communication Event Journal listing original tweets, posts, blogs articles with the DOI link
 - Examples / templates for tweets, videos, linkedin, website teasers
 - Impact measurement link and screenshots
- Complete the contact file with on the web published informations
 - https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BAYPb_mjCq9K91iRMumWbaKmMFLdJljQpDeJ8wALAAk/edit#gid=969377720
- Ideas
 - **Videos** (ca. 1 min) to be prepared to reflect the 12 Recommendations in the paper. Suggestion: to release one per month, linking back to the published paper, over the next year.
 - "How to" information sent out to partners so that all EOSC-Life resources can be entered into the Zenodo EOSC-Life community - final newsflash (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-life/>)
 - Link to General meeting discussions minutes for other ideas -> feasibility, prioritisation / distributing roles / agenda
- Agenda
 - Further related items to be discussed at meeting on Friday (18.8.)

Tchat:

Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) 15:10

Agree - brief summary of the Sustainability Manuscript initiative with a link to latest preprint
Les messages envoyés au "Chat de groupe de la réunion" apparaîtront aussi dans le chat de groupe dédié dans Chat de groupe

Vous 15:13
summary part by part (6 or 7)

Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) 15:14
Or summarise all parts in one text

Vous 15:17
https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#heading=h.96kfzkyl3key

jean-marie burel 15:24
I have to attend another meeting sorry. Please tag me with any tasks you wish me to look at

Vous 15:24
ok thanks Jean-Marie
jean-marie burel a quitté

Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) 15:30
very useful metrics platform

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) 15:32
Romain, can you download the list of blog sites as a CSV or XLS so I can add them to the list (submission of short summary article with link to paper and impactful image)

Vous 15:36
<https://www.altmetric.com/details/6193015#score>
as an example

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) 15:41
<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-life/>

Vous 15:43
I would like to open a communication materials doc for the paper

Vous 15:44
with "how to" section, "to do list" section, list of blogs / referent links appearing
and a first draft of agenda :)
and responsibilities distribution

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) 15:47
Ok, thanks Romain!

Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) 15:49
Time to refresh French :)

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) 15:50
I had 5 years of French in high school but completely overlaid by German now! :(

Arina Rybina (Euro-BiolImaging) 15:50

Arina Rybina (Euro-BiolImaging) 15:56

we have some table for this I think....with potential contributions / volunteers (From my side I could potentially start working on such type of activity probably mid/end Sept.)

Vous 15:59

we can also try "video sprint" with zoom recording
Philip.Gribbon a quitté

Arina Rybina (Euro-BiolImaging) 16:00

I can wear my EOSC-Life Outfit :D

Vous 16:04

Don't forget to be funny :)

Vous 16:04

from my side, I like very much communicating with (my) cat

Vous 16:12

you need to travel by train ;)
Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) a quitté

Meeting SP#33 04/08/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BiolImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **J-M Burel (Dundee, Euro-BiolImaging)**
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**
- **J-K Heriche (Euro-BiolImaging Bio-Hub, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)**
- **Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)**
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER)**
- **Katrina Exter (VLIZ)**
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**

Apologized: Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)
Bénédicte Madon (DANUBIUS-RI, Universidad de Sevilla)
Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)

Agenda

- *Editor commentary and response (with letter)*
- Trying to complete all things before next Friday 4th august DONE

- NB will respond final OK to the editors (on behalf of Phil and editorial team)
DONE
- Friday: Editorial decision on submission - send to the authors for validation
- *Submission (and before, check asked to the list of authors: 1 week proposed(?))*
- Submitted 1 week later (Friday 11th aout)

Notes & Actions to be done

We plan to check all commentaries from EMBOJ editor and validate proposed modifications and adds prior to official submission (below)

This meeting (open to all co-authors) will also permit to act the future agenda and cover letter

<p>A question we have for you is if this piece is meant to be the sole summary statement planned for this consortium? As you may imagine this is an important consideration for such a broad scope project from our side, and we appreciate your feedback on this. Overall, we aim to avoid largely redundant statements in different journals.</p> <p>Some points and comments in more detail on the text and structure:</p>	<p>Rep from Niklas to the editor: Dear Daniel,</p> <p>As the EOSC-Life coordinator I am responding on behalf of Phil Gribbon who unfortunately experiences difficulties sending emails remotely. We wanted to provide you with a quick response but to be clear: Phil remains the main contact for the submission although it would be helpful if you could cc me and Romain on any correspondence in the next week. We would like to provide a full submission to EMBO J and will submit a manuscript addressing your comments shortly.</p> <p>I also want to provide reassurance on redundant statements and competing publications. To my knowledge as the project coordinator, there are no other papers with this scope planned and that this manuscript represents the main summary from EOSC-Life. There are papers planned on the individual project components but this paper is the main summary with synthesis and forward-looking recommendations and we would hope that the EMBO J readership will find this interesting and clarifying.</p>
<p>0) Length and number figures boxes certainly on the longer side, but seems well justified and ok (compare Miura et al example attached).</p>	<p>Thanks for the editors to accept a special format for this special article</p>
<p>1) the abstract feels a bit dry and rather long (<200 words would usually be our recommendation). Please shorten.</p>	<p>Abstract was reshaped and reviewed by the editorial team of the paper in 200 words</p>
<p>2) It would be important in our view to complement the analysis in how</p>	<p>A specific effort was made after the recommendations presentation to explain for each</p>

<p>far FAIR is realizable in fact. Full and formal FAIR seems very hard to achieve, and as often defining a more circumspect goal seems completely fine.</p>	<p>recommendation how each action helps or is mandatory for FAIR implementation (see Table-2 and Box-8). As this crosswalk is a bit complex, we summarised it in a table before the box</p>
<p>3) The artwork appears mature and probably would likely only need a minor rework by our graphics team.</p>	<p>Thank you for your feedback. We are available for making adaptations and implementing your recommendations as required for improving the quality. We will appreciate help and support by the EMBO Journal graphics team in this process.</p>
<p>4) Please organise the majority of authors in an 'Appendix 1' (see attached ELIXIR commentary example for comparison).</p>	<p>In this case, as it is a radical collaboration paper (each author takes an active part in writing and editing, see supplementary information 1) and we would like to ask the editor kindly for permission to keep the entire list. We also feel that it is also important to align with the FAIR principles by clearly demonstrating the provenance of the work performed by means of an easily findable record of authorship at the start of the manuscript. Linked to this, each research Infrastructure is preparing to highlight this publication via its own collection and website and it has prepared an appropriate communication plan addressed to its own community (linkedIn, Tweeter, newsletters, youtube video and other traditional ways are planned for each of the 13 RI partners)</p>
<p>5) the URL links should best go into a Box. (see again Miura et al).</p>	<p>We ve integrated links of the Table 1 in a Box.</p>
<p>6) Initials and acrnymys seem a bit excessive. Please reconsider if all of them are needed. They should be introcuded at first mention in the running text.</p>	<p>Initials and acronyms were reduced, evident one erased and only 1 time used were only kept if necessary</p>
<p>7) The current 'Supplementary Information' would need to be changed into an 'Appendix 2'</p>	<p>Done</p>
<p>COVER LETTER to Editor</p>	<p>https://docs.google.com/document/d/1POfHKft3nNP0gyDcEx9cGQUxQJu71mtE4jUs-i87pgM/edit TO BE CHANGED</p>
<p>RESPONSE from Editor to Niklas</p>	<p>Thank you for the swift response. Again, we are very glad to see your interest for sharing your summary on the EOSC project work and guidelines in the EMBO Journal. I also appreciate your confirmation regarding potential alternative commentaries.</p>

	<p>Please refer to our exchange at formal full submission. Note that I will be out of office for the next two weeks, but look forward to taking this swiftly on afterwards. Given the maturity of text and figures, this should be a smooth, expedited process.</p>
<p>EMBOJ Submission announcement to co-authors</p>	<p>Dear Co-authors</p> <p>As announced throughout the last emails and meetings, we asked the EMBO Journal editors if submission of our EOSC-Life Sustainability paper would align with the journal's scope.</p> <p>The responses of editors were mostly positive (see the rolling notes), and they have proposed to us some relatively minor modifications to increase the chance of a successful and rapid review. The editorial team proceeded to make required changes (see the table in the meeting notes SP#33 - even if it is a holiday period, we thank those of you that had the opportunity to participate). We are now ready to resubmit officially the article in the EMBO Journal, on Friday 11th of August.</p> <p>The updated paper version is placed in preprint on Zenodo (Version 4 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8059830) to permit to all co-authors approving the submitted version according to the journal author requirements https://www.embopress.org/page/journal/14602075/authorguide#authorshipguidelines. If no critical feedback is received before this date, we will submit the article with the proposed changes.</p> <p>On behalf of the editorial team, Romain.</p>

Meeting SP#32 28/07/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)

- J-M Burel (Dundee, Euro-Biolmaging)
- Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)
- J-K Heriche (*Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, EMBL Heidelberg*)
- Bénédicte Madon (DANUBIUS-RI, Universidad de Sevilla)
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)

Agenda

- EMBOJ discussion
- Points EMBOJ submission
 - **LINK TO THE EMBOJ VERSION**
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bO2dzUSf05_R_sCnIRkoWhKrEDtf_YtTuTr5Ki5sivE/edit?usp=sharing
 - Article type= Commentary?
 - Length: seems OK
 - Author list: must be kept as possible (radical collaboration)
 - Cover letter: strategic -> aims of the paper: no other equivalent for EOSC Life in other journals -> **Phil have a last look on it**
LINK TO THE COVER LETTER
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1POfHKft3nNP0gyDcEx9cGQUxQJu71mtE4jUs-i87pgM/edit>
 - ...
 - FORGOTTEN: RESPONSES TO EDITORS POINT per POINT
- AOB

Notes & Actions to be done

ACTIONS: Mail to all authors after decision

NB-> last read on the version

Timing ->

- Trying to complete all things before next Friday 4th aout
- NB will respond final OK to the editors (on behalf of Phil and editorial team)
- Friday: Editorial decision on submission - send to the authors for validation
- Submitted 1 week later (Friday 11th aout)

From: d.klimmeck@embojournal.org <d.klimmeck@embojournal.org>

Sent: 26 July 2023 13:11

To: Philip Gribbon

Subject: Your presubmission enquiry (EMBOJ-2023-115008P)

Fraunhofer IME/ITMP Security Warning: This is an external message! Don't open any attachment, copy or follow links or forward this message unless you trust the sender's address.

Dear Dr Philip Gribbon,

Thank you again for enquiring about the potential suitability of your commentary manuscript for the EMBO Journal. I now went through your commentary proposal and also discussed it with other members of the editorial team including our Head of Scientific Publications Bernd Pulverer. I am happy to say that we strongly encourage full submission to the EMBO Journal,

as we consider it a core function of a leading European community journal to offer a platform for communicating infrastructure milestones such as this one.

A question we have for you is if this piece is meant to be the sole summary statement planned for this consortium? As you may imagine this is an important consideration for such a broad scope project from our side, and we appreciate your feedback on this. Overall, we aim to avoid largely redundant statements in different journals.

NB Another paper is planned, but will not overlap

Some points and comments in more detail on the text and structure:

0) Length and number figures boxes certainly on the longer side, but seems well justified and ok (compare Miura et al example attached).

1) the abstract feels a bit dry and rather long (<200 words would usually be our recommendation). Please shorten. -> **Phil will make a first try, Arina, Jean-Marie and Romain will work on it as well.**

2) It would be important in our view to complement the analysis in how far FAIR is realizable in fact. Full and formal FAIR seems very hard to achieve, and as often defining a more circumspect goal seems completely fine.

Use the FAIR DSM assessment process example as a methodology to understand the FAIR level. "FAIR as a spectrum" where we bring support to the recommendations in order to progress the status for a specific tool or resource (Romain and JMB to prepare a para on this)

Be PREPARED (and Act Timely) extension -> Arina for practical implementations (Any more ideas: Romain - Jean Marie happy to participate)

3) The artwork appears mature and probably would likely only need a minor rework by our graphics team. (congrats Arina!!!) 😊

4) Please organise the majority of authors in an 'Appendix 1' (see attached ELIXIR commentary example for comparison).

Recognition of authors is part of the sustainability of the outcomes. Add a sentence - continuing to build with communications. All must be recognised (linked to the community building). Many arguments (Also in recommendations like Community building - rewards -

Visibility - career recognition -> formally recognize as it is “radical collaboration = 1 place for each” Phil will lead a response on it - Romain will transmit to editors

5) the URL links should best go into a Box. (see again Miura et al). **Romain & Phil will provide a proposal, Arina will help** (Sara will advise if graphical solutions are expectable)

6) Initials and acronyms seem a bit excessive. Please reconsider if all of them are needed. They should be introduced at first mention in the running text. (some acronyms are not required-> to be erase) **Phil will have a global check**

7) The current 'Supplementary Information' would need to be changed into an 'Appendix 2' **Phil will have a global check**

I hope above is useful.

I am looking forward to your formal full submission and more exchange on this.

*Best regards,
Daniel Klimmeck*

*Daniel Klimmeck, PhD
Senior Editor
The EMBO Journal*

To submit your manuscript, please follow this link.

<https://emboj.msubmit.net/cgi-bin/main.plex?el=A4li7zHX5A5EEjj5I4A9ftdGL0ul34lfdBLV7vPo4ECNAY>

Please do not share this URL as it will give anyone who clicks it access to your account.

***Please note that for techn*

POINT FROM HELEN

I've shared the preprint around various groups and had excellent feedback. A colleague has pointed out that we don't address environmental sustainability.

He's written several papers on this and I wonder if it's worth adding an additional recommendation and/or adding some text on this in the paper? The first link below is principles for greener computational science, so a reference to these may be sufficient.

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s43588-023-00461-y>

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s43586-023-00202-5>

best wishes

**NB add out of scope of this particular study but important to be considered
Phil will adapt text to include it**

Meeting SP#31 21/07/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- J-M Burel (Dundee, Euro-Biolmaging)
- J-K Heriche (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, EMBL Heidelberg)

Agenda

●

Notes & Actions to be done

Dear Romain DAVID,

I recently sent you a list of journal recommendations for your manuscript "Sustainability of FAIR Life Science Resources and Projects: Lessons Learned from EOSC-Life Research Infrastructures", and I just wanted to check if I can help you with a transfer, or if you would like more journal recommendations.

If you would like to submit to one of the recommended journals, please reply to this email within the next 3 working days.

Alternatively, if none of the recommended journals are suitable for you, I would be happy to make additional suggestions, if available. If you have any specific requirements, such as for indexing or open access/non-open access, please let me know and I can look for journals that meet your requirements.

With kind regards,

Tushar Lokare

Editorial Submission Advisor

Springer Nature

—

Springer Nature Submission Support :

Dear Dr Romain DAVID,

My name is Tushar Lokare, and I am a Submission Editorial Advisor at the [Springer Nature Transfer Desk](#), a free service from Springer Nature. I help authors find the most suitable journal for their manuscript and provide assistance to minimise the time and effort spent on the submission process. I have closely looked at your manuscript and, using my subject area knowledge and our advanced journal matching technology, I recommend the following journal(s):

1. [Discover Sustainability](#) (Impact factor: 2.6, CiteScore: N/A, Author Satisfaction: 100%, Median time from submission to first decision: 26 days, Open Access, APC: EUR 940.00 | GBP 840.00 | USD 1240.00)

Discover Sustainability could be the best transfer destination for your paper as it all transfers of papers in fields relevant to sustainability, addressing social, environmental and technological challenges worldwide.

- Discover Sustainability is indexed in Scopus, Emerging Science Citation Index and DOAJ
- Editor-in-Chief, Professor Walter Leal Filho, is keen to receive manuscripts, and is supported by a prominent editorial board with a wide range of specialties
- Discover Sustainability has an extremely high rate of review for submissions
- Discover Sustainability provides rapid turnaround times. On average, submissions to the journal progress through peer review within one month.
- Discover Sustainability offers excellent support services that adhere to the high editorial and publishing standards of Springer Nature. The editorial team and publishing staff will guide you at every stage of a rapid and rigorous submission, review, and publication experience.
- Discover Sustainability publishes a wide range of article types, including but not limited to Research, Reviews, Perspectives, Comments, Brief Communications, Case Studies, Registered Reports, and Data Notes.

You can see the full quality and scope of their published article history here (<https://link.springer.com/search?query=&search-within=Journal&facet-journal-id=43621>). We hope you seriously consider this journal as a home for your paper.

2. [Humanities and Social Sciences Communications](#) (Impact factor: 2.731, CiteScore: 0.6, Author Satisfaction: 81%, Median time from submission to first decision: N/A, Open Access, APC: EUR 1240.00 | GBP 1140.00 | USD 1590.00)

I recommend you consider submitting your paper to Humanities & Social Sciences Communications (<https://www.nature.com/palcomms/>), an open access journal published by Springer Nature that publishes research across all areas of the humanities, and social and behavioural sciences, including relevant interdisciplinary research arising in, or informed by, the physical, life, clinical and environmental sciences. The journal recently received its first impact factor of 2.7, and is indexed in Scopus, Pubmed and Web of Science (Arts & Humanities Citation Index, Social Sciences Citation Index). Please note that from January 2015 until June 2020, this journal operated as Palgrave Communications.

The journal welcomes submissions for its general section as well as themed collections (see calls for papers here: <https://www.nature.com/palcomms/calls-for-papers>).

The journal strives for rapid peer review and the editors will assess your manuscript's suitability for peer review within approximately ten working days. Please note that to publish open access authors are required to pay an Article Processing Charge (APC). Further details on how to identify open access funding can be found at: <https://www.nature.com/palcomms/about/open-access>

Please let me know your choice within 7 days of receiving this message. In most cases, we will be able to send your manuscript, files and other information to the new journal for you, though you will have the opportunity to revise your manuscript before the editor receives it, if you wish. Please also

note that if you choose to transfer to one of our Hybrid/Open Choice journals, you have the option to publish your article open access if you wish.

Otherwise, if you have another Springer Nature journal in mind that you would like to transfer to, kindly let me know and I can, in most cases, transfer your manuscript automatically.

If you have any questions or need further assistance, please contact me by replying to this email.

With kind regards,

Tushar Lokare
Editorial Submission Advisor

Meeting SP#30 14/07/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Sara**
- **Bénédicte**
- **Jessica**
- **Jan-Willem**
- **Marianna Childress-Poli (Euro-Biolmaging comms manager)**

Agenda

- Discussion about BD&S
- Communication plan with videos
- Possible timeline

Notes & Actions to be done

Holidays

Phil G 27th July - 15th August (not available)

Romain Available through July and August

Sara Available through July and August

Arina (available 1st and 2nd week of August and around this need to see how I can contribute, goes on leave mid August - 1st week Sept)*

Other availability to be checked

[ull/10.15252/emj.2020107409](https://doi.org/10.15252/emj.2020107409) <https://www.embopress.org/doi/f>

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit#gid=519164427>

<https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/emboj.2018101215>

Contacts EMBO Journal:

Thomas Lemberger: <https://www.embl.org/people/person/thomas-leMBERGER/thomas.leMBERGER@embo.org>

and chief editor: bernd.pulverer@embo.org

Feedback BDS

Dear Dr. Gribbon

Reading through your abstract, it could be a fit for the journal as it focuses on an applied case of open data and its infrastructures. I suggest enhancing social reflections to see the data practices and reflections that emerge from them. Of course, this is based on a review of an abstract - and I don't make editorial decisions - but that is the input I can provide.

I suggest you review the journal's aims and scope (<https://journals.sagepub.com/aims-scope/BDS>) and read several articles (<https://journals.sagepub.com/home/BDS>) to consider how your work connects to ongoing debates/discussions featured in the journal. This will provide the best assessment of whether your work fits the scope. Regarding the format, you can check the submission guidelines for more details (<https://journals.sagepub.com/author-instructions/bds>).

Best,

Natalia Orrego

Big Data & Society Editorial Team

bdseditors@gmail.com <<mailto:bdseditors@gmail.com>>

On Wed, 12 Jul 2023 at 09:52, Philip Gribbon <Philip.Gribbon@itmp.fraunhofer.de> <<mailto:Philip.Gribbon@itmp.fraunhofer.de>> > wrote:

Dear BDS Editors,

We are currently looking to identify the optimal journal for a manuscript which addresses the sustainability of large scale data and software resources from the Life Science community. The manuscript describes, in some detail, the findings from a substantial collaborative project "EOSC-LIFE <https://www.eosc-life.eu/> " which is aligned with the European Open Science Cloud program.

The abstract is appended below and a preprint can be found on Zenodo here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8059831>

I would be very grateful if you could provide feedback on whether the topic of the manuscript matches the scope/aims of the BDS journal. If you decide that the content is relevant, we would be able to immediately submit the paper for consideration by the editors.

Thanks in advance for your kind input.

Sincerely,

Dr Philip Gribbon

Meeting SP#29 07/07/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Kim Gurwitz (ELIXIR/ EMBL-EBI)
- Bénédicte Madon (DANUBIUS)
- Henriette (EMBL)

Agenda

- State of the preprint <https://zenodo.org/record/8068648>
- Communication Plan discussion
- Communication material
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1BAYPb_mjCq9K91iRMumWbaKmMFLdJljQpDeJ8wALAAk/edit?usp=sharing

- Dissemination strategy AGM
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Mhy47DBzeqXz7XLNB3MDqB0-7rh_Lrsk/edit?usp=sharing&oid=116842745610159845034&rtpof=true&sd=true
- AOB (poster for IDW / RDA / others?)

Notes & Actions to be done

- Recommendations for the 1 minute video summaries
 - At least 1 person from each RI - each covers one of the recommendations from the paper
 - Note that you can do it for others recommendations focussing on your activities if you want (e.g. papers / tools / workshops outputs)
 - Common slide/background for all speakers with EOSC-LIFE Logo - ask Sara or Arina for suggestions for how to do this?
 - Introduce yourself and the RI for which you are a member (5 secs)
 - Describe the main activities of the RI in the area of Research Data Management, What are the key resources managed by the RI (15 seconds)
 - Outline the sustainability challenges faced by the RI - What we need to do as an RI to drive sustainability (15 seconds)
 - Link to one of the 12 recommendations contained in the paper
 - Examples of recommendation X are
 - We curate our data at source and aim to have “FAIR at point of data generation approach”
 - “We use OMOP formats for all of our clinical data as this aids analyses of anonymised clinical
 - Ask people to look at the paper
 - Last slide a QR code for people to access the paper from the video
 - Do not forget these informations in the metadata / and descriptions of your video
 - Title
 - RI denomination - authors
 - Topic: (title of the paper teaser)
 - Recommendation denomination
 - DOI !!
 - EOSC_Life & RI tag
 - Video dissemination
 - Each partner send it to us with metadata
 - We will provide a calendar for their diffusion on youtube and associated media (teaser Twitter / LinkedIn / webpage of the RI website / Newsletters / Youtube Channel if one?)
 - Checking with communication team for agreement or disclaimer if needed

- Overall dissemination strategy draft email with instructions on tweeting and use of linked, for example need to prepare individual image- Phil action to sit down Sarah for 30 minutes to prepare instructions

Recommendation	RI	Speaker
<i>BE RECOGNIZED: Build with experts</i>	<i>INSTRUCT? (linking experts in the calls) (DANUBIUS) (MIRRI)</i>	<i>Pauline Audergeon? (Bénédicte Madon) (Jean-Luc? -> reuse)</i>
<i>BE RECOGNIZED: Publish, communicate, disseminate</i>	<i>BBMRI</i>	<i>Petr Holub? (highlight recent publications on CRC project)</i>
<i>BE PRACTICAL: Demonstrate, not only tell</i>	<i>BBMRI</i>	<i>Michaela Th. Mayrhofer?</i>
<i>BE PRACTICAL: Plan training for acute and future needs</i>	<i>EuroBioImaging</i>	<i>Arina Rybina ? (Kim Gurwitz can contribute too from ELIXIR side, or Rebecca Ludwig from EATRIS)</i>
<i>BE PRACTICAL: Metadata makes FAIR</i>	<i>(EuroBioImaging) Romain as a EOSC TF FAIR Metrics Member</i>	<i>(Jean-Marie Burel? & Henriette)</i>
<i>BE READY: Be prepared, agile, act timely</i>	<i>ERINHA (be ready with ISIDORE for instance)</i>	<i>Romain David Jonathan Ewbank</i>
<i>BE READY: Curate NOW</i>	<i>EMBRC</i>	<i>Katrina Exter?</i>
<i>BE UNIFYING: Establish federated governance</i>	<i>ECRIN</i>	<i>Maria Panagiotopoulou?, Christian Ohmann?</i>
<i>BE UNIFYING: Harmonise and integrate</i>	<i>ELIXIR</i>	<i>Henriette Harmse</i>
<i>BE UNIFYING: Reward sustainability</i>	<i>ELIXIR (rewards globally from EOSC-Life)</i>	<i>Niklas?</i>
<i>BE CLEAR: Be open AND be inclusive</i>	<i>All?! Jessica? as a EOSC TF Sustainability Member</i>	
<i>BE CLEAR: Treat innovation and sustainability independently</i>	<i>EU-OPENSREEN</i>	<i>Phil Gribbon</i>

Actions

- To confirm that everybody is happy to do that
- To build the background slide/branding - sense check what is best with Sara/comms (Phil)

- *Models of tweets (and linkedIn posts), tags, #hashtag? #BeSustainable, Image personalised for each RI (and each author! Do not hesitate) (Romain)*
- *Mail to authors with a communication plan guideline (Phil for a draft with Sara)*
- *Send an invite for next week's call (Actual actions as a proposal for agenda)*

Meeting SP#28 09/06/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- *Romain David (ERINHA),*
- *Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)*
- *Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)*
- *B*

Agenda

- *Are we ready to submit?*
 - *9350 words with boxes (!)*
 - *To be discussed:*
 - *Links/acronym/reference validation to be finished*
 - *Reference on Zenodo for data: keep it in EOSC-Life outputs?*
 - *LINK:*
 - *Check if all RIs have at least 1 link to their website (MIRRI? Others?)*
 - *Link in table 1 in double OK?*
 - *Minor changes to be done in the figures (margin, logos, alignments) -> Romain, Arina?*
 - ***Bold in the paper?** -> review by Niklas, Phil and Jonathan this week-end?*
 - ***Submission on Monday Evening***
 - *Sup material: proposal on zenodo: rolling notes + excel sheet + summary and 1 sentence*
 - *Preprint on Zenodo after submission? **PG mail to editor for preprint possibility?***
 - *Preprints are defined as an author's version of a research manuscript prior to formal peer review at a journal, which is deposited on a public server (as described in Preprints for the life sciences. Science 352, 899–901; 2016).*
 - *Preprints may be posted at any time during the peer review process.*
- Posting of preprints is not considered to be a prior publication and will not jeopardize being considered for publication in Springer Nature journals.*

- Springer Nature has partnered with [Research Square](#) to provide *In Review*, a journal-integrated solution for preprint sharing. Please refer to our [In Review](#) page for more information.

- Other points?
- **MANY THANKS TO ALL EDITORS COMITEE MEMBERS**

Notes & Actions to be done

•

Meeting SP#27 02/06/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**

Agenda

- *Actions from last meeting*
 - JKH to reshape the paper from tuesday to next Friday
 - Before:
 - *Legends to be added (AR, RD)*
 - *Figures to be completed (AR)*
 - *Mailto all editors (PG) for reshaping*
 - *Mailto Niklas, Fredericke and Michael RAESS for perspectives*
- *Paper statement*
 - *Again 1000? words too long*
 - *Perspectives to be added*
 - *bold in the paper*
 - *Complete reviews from Sara, Romain, Arina -> **please other editors validate!***

Notes & Actions to be done

All: Check Legends and check recommendations

Romain: check editor requirements / check links /

Arina & Romain: check Figures

Phil & Jean-Marie: validate/erase all suggestions/comments in the paper-> make a count of the words -> send an email with new objectives of diminution if needed

Niklas->perspectives

AP Jessica: check

PG mail to editor for preprint possibility

PG mail to Jean-Karim to check with version (if one is reshaped on its side)

SCHEDULE

From monday to Thursday: last Editors Review

Thursday to Friday: Editors suggestions validations

Friday: submission decision

MAIL from PG

Dear Editorial team,

We will take the current version offline on Tuesday 30th May at 5pm for JK to do some final shaping.

https://docs.google.com/document/d/18hR9nQxH5R-r0u_utL2NvRTFAySIQvYX5H54q7vOrEY/edit#heading=h.3dy6vkm

Before then please check the text, as we need to lower the wordcount by 600 words through removing duplications and placing non-core text in appendices.

Niklas / Friederike -could you take a look at the final perspectives section and add your final thoughts as the overview "wrap-up"

Thanks a lot and have a great weekend.

Best

Phil + Romain

Meeting SP#26 26/05/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- *Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI) (appologize)*
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**

Agenda

- *Actions from last meeting*
- *Paper statement*
 - *1000 words too long*
 - *Perspectives to be added*
 - *Box and bold in the paper*

Notes & Actions to be done

JKH to reshape the paper from tuesday to next Friday

Before:

- Legends to be added (AR, RD)
- Figures to be completed (AR)
- Mailto all editors (PG) for reshaping
- Mailto Niklas, Fredericke and Michael RAESS for perspectives

Meeting SP#25 19/05/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)
- Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)

Agenda

- Actions from last meeting
 - Recommendations checking
 - Iterative format for the figure in recommendations section
 - Icons in the figure
- Paper statement
 - Review from authors closed at noon today, almost 25 reviewers
 - Paper too long (almost 8800 words)
 - Which part / redundancies to be moved ?
 - Missing:
 - Abstract needed
 - Perspective in the last part after recommendations?
 - To be improved:
 - Images and Figures legends upgraded
 - Some refs are missing, we have to tag peoples who have it or erase it
 - Some sentence need to be clarified (help from a native speaker should be better)
 - Other suggestions
 - Bold in each part for key points (easier read)
 - Reference the recommendation number in the text?
- Next step(s)?

Notes & Actions to be done

- Jean-Karim: to extract content from MT to supplementary material
- Flag where recommendations are supported by the main text (Jess K to start)

- *General ideas should be findable / relatable in the text*
- *Phil G - draft abstract*
- *Perspective paragraph (< 200 words). Phil G to contact NB and FSK and Michael Raess) to ask to prepare text which pulls everything together and links our experience in EOSC-LIFE to guidance that we would propose to adjacent EOSC communities*
- *Jean-K Section 1.D.iii to be reorganized to better accommodate the workflow section also to be clarified /reduced /transferred to supplementary section*
- *Figure owners to recheck that figures are referenced in text (ARy / JK*
- *Arina: Review Training and Open Calls / use cases Sections (together with JMB),*
- *Experts (eg training) to review non-expert sections (explain if tagging people what we need, eg., is it understandable, clear, missing key points? etc)*
- *Ensure FAIRsharing cataloging of the resources identified in the paper*
 - *Editorial team to liaise with Allyson and Sussana A S, to align on this objective*
 - *Should be an aim of the overall project finalization following the AGM*
- *Phil G to check-in with editors if highlighted text / boxes are allowed for additional emphasis*
- *Jessica: will go through Recommendations section + tag recos in the text [RECO-X]*
- *Perspectives Section: Phil drafting, all to contribute to content*
- *Arina additional action points: review ISIDORE Section in Supplementary, help completing Figure 5 drafted by RD, and help visualizing table with tools made by JMB - if needed*
- *Romain Recommendation Figure + link tables to be reorganised + citations to be checked (double check for another welcome) + adding ideas for Friedericke and Niklas in perspectives + review radical collaboration part in sup material*

TO BE ATTRIBUTED:

- *If boxes and bold sentences are allowed by the editor: who makes the first try?*
- *Sup documents on Zenodo*
- *Any support for mind maps with EOSC-Life FAIR-Sharing?*
- *Mail for missing references: to be done next week*

...

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https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

Arina Rybina à Tout le monde 13:06

Prefer to have more time as well to finalise solidly

Arina Rybina à Tout le monde 13:12

Suggestion:we could insert some visual labels for the three and label the bullet points accordingly

Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) à Tout le monde 13:27

I'm not sure if Niklas is too close to EOSC-Life

I was thinking more of someone who is part of LS community but not EOSC-Life itself

Arina Rybina à Tout le monde 13:29

Maybe Michael Raess could help here - LS RI Strategy Board and EOSC-Life WP8

Vous à Tout le monde 13:31

+1 for Michael

1000 to be removed

Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) à Tout le monde 13:44

I will need to leave now. I will try to start going through the recommendations and crosschecking it with the text later this afternoon.

Vous à Tout le monde 13:45

thanks Jessica!

jean-marie burel à Tout le monde 13:48

<https://fairassist.org/#/>

Arina Rybina à Tout le monde 13:54

Maybe also checking on info boxes? 😊

If possible to have them...

jean-marie burel à Tout le monde 13:58

I have to go to another meeting

Vous 13:58

thank you Jean-Marie

Meeting template SP#24 12/05/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-Biomed Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)
- Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)
- Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)
- Martin Weise (TU Wien)
- Rafeale Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)
- Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - Paper reshaping phase 2 (Phil)
ADDs (and COMMENTS) in suggestion mode now!
Shortening when possible more than adding
Please reword and write instead of comment as possible as it is!
https://docs.google.com/document/d/18hR9nQxH5R-r0u_utL2NvRTFAySIQvYX5H54q7vOrEY/edit?usp=sharing
 - Figure Work
 - Authoring checking

- *Recommendations to be discussed*

Make you research project

- *Agenda and actions until submission*
 - *Next plan: core team to make changes by Monday 15th May afternoon 4 PM CEST, after whole manuscript will be shared with all authors for reviewing, review will be closed 22th of May. Next core edit writing meeting Tue/Wed 24-25th, Submission envisioned 26th May!*

Notes & actions

Sup material: JMB will propose a table

Vous voyez actuellement l'écran de Arina Rybina Options d'affichage

RESHAPED_Sustainability of FAIR Life Science Resources...

- Suitable and continually-relevant access technologies and methodologies for human and machine consumers
- Online archives/portals
- The adoption of policies concerning the permanence of storing and sharing the provenance (meta)data, and providing the necessary FAI (especially for sensitive information), updating, and versioning

Key points influencing the sustainability of provenance information include that when data are moved from researcher to researcher, and "units" of provenance are created each time, a distributed network of provenance information is created. Each unit in this network should receive a PID, and these links need to be maintained to ensure the sustainability of the provenance information. For the provenance itself to be trustworthy, appropriate cryptographic techniques are essential (e.g. hashes and digital signatures, combined with security policies).

EOSC-Life developed the "Common Provenance Model" (CPM) (Witmer et al, 2022) which

Participants: Philip Gribbon, ERINHA AISBL, Jean-Marie Burel, Arina Rybina, Jessica Klemmeier (EMBL), J-K, Henriette Harmse, Michaela Th Mayrhofer, rafaelematteoni

Vous voyez actuellement l'écran de Arina Rybina Options d'affichage

RESHAPED_Sustainability of FAIR Life S...

Challenge: Findability of resources (Sensitive data Q)

Methodology: Iterative & interdisciplinary consensus (Version 1, 2, 3)

Sustainable Outcome: Categorisation system & toolbox (Sensitive data Q)

Participants: Jean-Marie Burel, ERINHA AISBL, Arina Rybina, Jessica Klemmeier (EMBL), J-K, Henriette Harmse, Philip Gribbon, Martin Weise, Michaela Th Mayrhofer, rafaelematteoni

...

Actions to be done

...

#Copy of tchat

13:04:25 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vlmM3pSxFbwOotx_U/edit#

13:08:29 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

The link to the draft "RESHAPED" is in the rolling notes, suggestions from each on recommendations will be copy / paste in

13:09:09 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

+ 1 Table with links to resources

13:09:20 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

link to the reshaped paper:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/18hR9nQxH5R-r0u_utL2NvRTFAySIQvYX5H54q7vOrEY/edit?usp=sharing

13:09:21 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

+1 Table with links

13:09:42 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

+1 for the table of supplementary resources

13:10:18 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

Supplementary S4 to be linked in the text where feasible

13:12:55 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

table with all link should also be Added in the ref

13:13:24 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

and accronyms and abbreviations alos

13:13:26 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

also

13:14:19 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

sustainable: a "copy / intro for ressources" in zenodo could work?

13:14:58 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

Do we have a references limit (eg. 20 references max)?

13:16:30 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

No, I Don't remember if this

13:16:41 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

I ll check again

13:22:25 From Philip Gribbon to Everyone:

I can hear you

13:22:35 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

you are frozen

13:22:54 From Philip Gribbon to Everyone:

I will leave and come back

13:22:59 From ERINHA AISBL to Everyone:

yes

13:28:03 From J-K to Everyone:

Where do the 3 pillars appear? Or should that be 5 pillars?

13:30:27 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

+1 to final text firstr

13:32:19 From Martin Weise to Everyone:

Sorry for being late

13:32:59 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

yes

13:37:10 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

Sorry will be right back

13:38:42 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/18hR9nQxH5R-r0u_utL2NvRTFAySIQvYX5H54q7vOrEY/edit#

13:47:32 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

Austria too

13:47:56 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

+1 to Arina

13:49:21 From Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) to Everyone:

Perhaps also as a contribution to the EOSC Symposium in September?

13:51:44 From rafaematteoni to Everyone:

Many thanks Philipp, Romain and All!

13:51:54 From Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) to Everyone:

+1 thanks a lot!

13:51:58 From Michaela Th Mayrhofer to Everyone:

+1

13:53:35 From Arina Rybina to Everyone:

+1 Michaela!

Meeting template SP#23 09/05/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)**
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- **Ziaurrehman Tanoli (FIMM/UH)**

Apologies

- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**

Agenda

- **Actions decided last meeting**
 - **Paper reshaping (Phil)**
 - **Figure Work**
 - **Authoring checking (postponed)**
 -

Notes

Phil have to continue reshaping (2000+ words to be extracted more)

KE EOSC Life description can be erased -> Phil will put a part of them in sup mat

business part to be ameliorated

RD a piece of work considering sovereignty challenge must be included in the “business” part

Arina : Peoples to be tagged in figures staff

Phil and Romain: recommendations will be open to review for more impactful presentation; Read (only!) of the entire paper, even if in reshaping state will be allowed for better understanding recommendations provenance and justification:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1etp4x48j1kQQRqjm4KdSCzzNtyZspiTGKv7mdbsh2kU/edit?usp=sharing>

RECOMMENDATIONS to be reviewed:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1NCJVUBbxu782DFJ81u129oknbz0sR-eG0NEryfsUZJs/edit?usp=sharing>

...

Actions to be done

...

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Meeting template SP#22 28/04/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)**
- ...

Appologize

- **Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EBI)**
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**

Agenda

- *Last run before reshaping: deadline this afternoon*
- *To be done this afternoon:*
 - *ISIDORE in the discussion (in progress, copy/paste to be done)*
 - *Paper sprint Training part at 15:00PM (Zoom link :)*
 - *Progress in figures*
 - *...*
- *Points / issues to be solved*
 - *Lack of references / links to EOSC -> Ugis proposed a table*
 - *redundancy (HP)*
 - *need to have a coherent set of sustainability definitions (HP).*
 - *There's also some context missing for the landscape (HP).*
 - *Recommendations that emerge from the paper -> to be checked by reshaping? NB, RD, .. others?*
 - *two 'layers' of sustainability discussion? (Jessica)*
 - *Others*
- *Reshaping team:*
 - *Phil*
 - *Helen*
 - *Niklas*
 - *...*
- *English rewording / editing: Sara, Jonathan, ...*
- *Submission the 8th of may?*

Notes / Actions to be done

Phil will close the draft at 5 pm today

ISIDORE part wil arrive by the end of the week end

Figures on recommendations systemic relation is needed

10 reco at the end, 2 missing, but will extract them from the paper content

An acronym will be provided for the 10 reco if possible

Phil will work 1 week offline, 2 tables to be provided ASAP

- *1 By UGIS for links with EOSC*
- *1 By Katrina for Demonstrators (if possible)*

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Meeting template SP#21 21/04/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)
- Rafeale Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)
- Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)
- Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)
- ...

Appologize

-

Agenda

- General point
- New timeline
- ISIDORE Part in the discussion (validated)
- BY-COVID mention as a facilitator in the end??

Notes

The next steps are:

1) Before the next meeting (28th April 1pm), we will complete the text with a focus on: i) discussion (lead PG and RD) and; ii) reflecting on how best practice established in EOSC-LIFE may be applied directly in the ISIDORE setting (lead RD).

2) **At 5pm on the 28th April**, the document will be taken off-line and then finalised in Word (lead PG). If there specific inputs are necessary, we will make direct requests to authors.

3) On the 5th May, the final version will be discussed in weekly call.

4) During w/c 8th May, the paper will be submitted to "Sustainability Science"

One additional request to native speakers is to please review the document before the 28th April.

...

Actions to be done

...

#Copy of tchat

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Meeting (regular friday) SP#20 14/04/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- Maddalena Fratelli
- Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)
- Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)
- Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)
- **Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)**
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)
- Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- Katrina Exter (EMBRC)
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)
- Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jing Tang (EATRIS)
- Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)
- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**
- Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)
- Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)
- Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)
- Dario Longo (Euro-BioImaging Med-Hub, CNR)
- Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)
- Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)
- Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)
- Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EBI)
- Ziaurrehman Tanoli (FIMM/UH)
- Isabelle Perseil (INSERM)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Maddalena Fratelli
- Jonathan Tedds
- Paolo Romano
- Michi Mayrhofer (BBMRI)
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Appologize

- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - Cleaning sprint wrap up
 - New part for training -> sprint needed?
 - Uses cases less long and Uses cases more focused on sustainability challenges as possible as it is (see notes from 17/03/2023)(11 000 words now) + parts to be put in sup material
 - Table of uses cases (Jean-Marie+ Katrina for next Friday) + a figure? will depend on what important is emerging on figures (e.g. workflow and metadata)
- Rewording suggestion validation (team of english native speakers?)
- Figure statement
- Editor instructions: (type proposal: overview article 8 000 words)
<https://www.springer.com/journal/11625/submission-guidelines#Instructions%20for%20Authors%20Types%20of%20articles>
- Copyright and license term – CC BY Open Choice articles do not require transfer of copyright as the copyright remains with the author. In opting for open access, the author(s) agree to publish the article under the Creative Commons Attribution License. APC : 2690 euros
- next steps

Notes

...

Actions to be done

...

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Meeting CLEANING SPRINT SP#19 11/04/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**

- *Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)*
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- *Katrina Exter (EMBRIC)*
- *Harald Wagener (CHARITE)*
- *Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)*
- *Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)*
- *Jing Tang (EATRIS)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)*
- ***Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)***
- *Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)*
- *Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)*
- *Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Dario Longo (Euro-Biolmaging Med-Hub, CNR)*
- *Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England*
- *Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)*
- ***Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)***
- *Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)*
- *Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EBI)*
- *Ziaurrehman Tanoli (FIMM/UH)*
- *Isabelle Perseil (INSERM)*
- *Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)*
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli*
- *Jonathan Tedds*
- *Paolo Romano*
- ***Michi Mayrhofer (BBMRI)***
- ***Add your name and affiliation and PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!***

Appologize

- *Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli*
- *Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)*

Agenda

- *recentering the paper on the 3 pillars as discussed during last group meeting,*
- *extracting the materials not directly required for the paper (materials could be used as supplement and/or used for the final EOSC report)*
- *finding the best approach to tackle the training aspect raised across the paper.*

- AOB

Notes

- JMB:
 - Case studies section:
 - kept one detailed case study. The other case studies to be added as supplement material.
 - To review: List of tools/resource like RO-Crate, Workflow used before being introduced

...

Actions to be done

...

#Copy of tchat

...

Meeting template SP#18 07/04/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**

Sprint objectives / discussion on next steps

Meeting template SP#17 24/03/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel (EuBI)**
- *Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)*
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- *Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)*
- **Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)**
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)*
- **Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)**
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- **Harald Wagener (CHARITE)**

- Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
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- Dario Longo (Euro-Biomed Med-Hub, CNR)
- Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England
- **Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)**
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)
- Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EBI)
- Ziaurrehman Tanoli (FIMM/UH)
- Isabelle Perseil (INSERM)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Maddalena Fratelli
- Jonathan Tedds
- Paolo Romano
- **Rudolf Wittner (WP6)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- Romain David (ERINHA), Travel to RDA Plenary
-

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - **Paper writing sprints in April**
 - mini-groups to focus on sections
 - Tuesday 28/03 Working on Section 2. 10-12 CET Key challenges of sustainability
 -
- Tasks to be completed for 24/03
 - **Align to Purpose of EOSC -LIFE (from the website)**
 - The project publishes 'FAIR' data and a catalogue of services provided by participating RIs that enable the management, storage and reuse of data in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
 - The project ensures that this space is accessible to European research communities

- *Re-introduce, the underlying 3 pillars of technical, legal and financial sustainability as a thread through the text (how does it all fall together)*
 - editorial team responsibility
 - *How do the use cases connect to the 3 challenges*
 - *need to make sure that the descriptions are aligned to the wider message of the paper*
 - *How do we sustain each element (try not to*
 - *Use the example as the toolbox for sharing sensitive data, which is well explained and connection to sustainability os clearly made*
 - *Sustainability of i) tools, ii)resources, iii)training, iv) open-science (1500 words per section)*
- *Figures should align and reiterate the content (eg the three pillars of sustainability)*
- *Figure 2 workflow link to Demo6 text and activities (J-K, PA)*
- *Figure 4 - maturity analysis - need first version from HP*
- **focus on empty parts**
- **look at figures (first draft)**
 - Sara:
 - <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Zr1UR5H4cTFIFZHkz6jveRR0GmQG56fx>
-
- *reduce cases studies / too much longer parts (11500+ words yet)*
 - *Review targets of case studies. (already covered above)*
- *ensure all is focused on sustainability challenge, how it works well AND NOT, lessons learned*
- *reword bullets points in more narrative form*
- *Citations to be completed: please put DOI or link in a comment*
- **When task done, you can erase notification**

Notes

- *Mini-groups:*
 - *Tuesday 28/03 Working on Section 2. 10-12 CET Key challenges of sustainability*
- *Arina/Kim: many aspects in the paper, but it seems to go in several directions. Re-introduce pillars (Phil)*
 - *Jessica: missing connection between the sections*

...

Actions to be done

...

#Copy of tchat

Meeting template SP#16 17/03/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel**
- *Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)*
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- *Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)*
- **Henriette Harmse (EMBL-EBI)**
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)*
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
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- *Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)*
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-Bioluming Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
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- *Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)*
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- *Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)*
- *Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER)*
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- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli*
- *Jonathan Tedds*
- *Paolo Romano*
- **Add your name and affiliation and PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

-

Agenda

- Paper sprint results
- Point arising after sprints about
 - Uses cases more focused on sustainability challenges as possible as it is
 - Training section -> is 2)A)f) section not enough? (Training word 50 times in the draft)
 - Discussion
 - DISCUSSION: Technical implementations empty (!)
 - DISCUSSION: Section Proposed by Isabelle: Exploitation and markets for sustainability
- Next sprints:
 - to be organized by sections leaders (smaller groups)
 - co-writers can also participate if not able to assist (use tagging, be responsive!)
 - **Sections sprints within 2 weeks (next week RDA Plenary takes place)**
 - **2 general sprint will be organized Tuesday 4th april 14pm and Tuesday 11th april 14pm (Phil G to send out invites) each meeting 1 hr**
- Tasks for next week: BEFORE FRIDAY
 - **focus on empty parts**
 - reword bullets points in more narrative form
 - reduce cases studies / too much longer parts (11500+ words yet)
 - ensure all is focused on sustainability challenge, how it works well

AND NOT, lessons learned, **Recommendations**

 - Citations to be completed: please put DOI or link in a comment
 - **When task done, you can erase notification**
 - First draft of figure for Friday OK for all?
- Questions?
- Reminder: radical collaboration: try to work on it 5 to 10 minutes
- Next Friday meeting: RD not able to assist: another person to lead the meeting? -> Thanks Jean-Marie for taking the lead!
- AOB?

Notes

Create a glossary about sustainability (KE JK)

Additional document (for parts that can be extract) (at least for cases studies) KE, PGr, JK and a table with link to external content (and zenodo supp material if not allowed by the journal)

NEW PARAGRAPH! Training part combating all training related content to be reorganized with content AR, JMB, KG, RL, WP9 and WP4 at least (expert engaging in training) -> TAGG all persons that are talking about training

Figure spring at the end (but need to have a draft for each) AR, SC, RD
 2 or 3 key components for sustainability (short term, mid term, long term) a table at the end of the paper MP Maria will suggest an empty table AR (a kind of "take home message" + recommendations box to summarize)

Open science / JK, HW and JKH will try to homogenize with free softwares and open codes and ... -> to be drafted in Discussion how it could help as a key point for organization 'e.g. participative coding, other implications with funders (storage, and... JMB) -> JKH to be coupled with data aspects (ease of access for instance) upstream ecosystem to be maintainable

JMB to prepare an agenda for next Friday meeting (RD can help), will provide invitations and chair the next meeting

The screenshot shows a Google Docs document titled "EOSC-Life Sustainability paper Rolling notes" during a meeting. The document content is as follows:

Agenda

- Paper sprint results
 - Point arising after sprints about
 - Uses cases more focused on sustainability challenges as possible as it is
 - Training section -> is 2(A)e) section not enough? (Training word 50 times in the draft)
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 - reword bullets points in more narrative form
 - reduce cases studies / too much longer parts (11500+ words yet)
 - ensure all is focused on sustainability challenge, how it works well AND NOT lessons learned, Recommendations
 - Citations to be completed: please put DOI or link in a comment

On the right side of the screen, a list of participants is shown:

- Romain David - ERINHA AISBL (Hôte, moi)
- JK Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) (Invité)
- AR Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) (Invité)
- PG Phil Gribbon (Invité)
- KE Katrina Exter (VLIZ) (Invité)
- Harald Wagener (Invité)
- Henriette Harmse (Invité)
- J Jean-Karim Heriche (Invité)
- JB jean-marie burel (Invité)
- MP Maria Panagiotopoulou (Invité)
- R rafaeldomattoni (Invité)
- U Ugis Sarkans (Invité)

Actions to be done

#Copy of tchat

Hello everyone!

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:03

I have a problem with sound.

Maria Panagiotopoulou à Tout le monde 13:22

Maybe also highlight the "sustainability approach" of trainings like some trainings may be available in YouTube beyond the project duration, or in platforms of specific RIs, or integrating in training programmes of specific RIs, or being updated/recycled to serve other projects...etc

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:22

agree with Jessica and Maria

Kim Gurwitz à Tout le monde 13:24
apologies for joining late. a meeting over ran

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:26
beginning April?

Vous à Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) (Message direct) 13:27
4th april for the general sprint

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:28
Easter holidays here start on 1 April so last week of March works better for me :)

Maria Panagiotopoulou à Tout le monde 13:29
Also what JK suggests

Katrina Exter (VLIZ) à Tout le monde 13:29
both weeks of April are bad here

Maria Panagiotopoulou à Tout le monde 13:29
Last Week of March?

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:29
last week in March is ISIDORe AGM plus travelling..

Katrina Exter (VLIZ) à Tout le monde 13:30
we will need 2 sprints!

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:30
good compromise!

shall we have some recommendations box?

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:32
so that it is clearly visible?

Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) à Tout le monde 13:32
Collect potential recommendations as bullets somewhere central?

Phil Gribbon à Tout le monde 13:33
sorry, I have to leave for the conference session

Maria Panagiotopoulou à Tout le monde 13:36
To be fair maybe we do need a "figure sprint" also with WP10 for "Professional" ideas?
Maybe as a very last step before finalisation

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:37
figure sprint at later stage sounds ok :)

Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) à Tout le monde 13:37
There is already the Key Exploitable Results for EOSC-Life, no?

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:38
we could also include Guidelines developed
tthis is ususally less visible to outside

Jessica Klemeier (EMBL) à Tout le monde 13:39
<https://zenodo.org/record/7404164#.ZBRfiPbMK3B>
Here's the link to the summary report - it's together with other H2020 projects
<https://zenodo.org/record/7401539#.ZBRf8fbMK3A>
full report here

Harald Wagener 13:56
free services suddenly going away or charging, latest example: docker
I have to head out now

Maria Panagiotopoulou 13:58
thank you & Phil for organising

Meeting Paper sprint 2 SP#15 17/03/2023 14:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Marie Burel**
- *Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)*
- *Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)*
- *Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)*
- *Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- **Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)**
- *Katrina Exter (EMBRC)*
- **Harald Wagener (CHARITE)**
- *Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- **Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)**
- *Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)*
- *Jing Tang (EATRIS)*
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- *Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)*
- *Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)*
- *Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Dario Longo (Euro-BioImaging Med-Hub, CNR)*
- **Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England**
- *Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)*
- *Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)*
- *Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)*
- *Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)*
- **Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER)**
- *Ugis Sarkans (EGI)*
- **Ziaurrehman Tanoli (FIMM/UH)**
- **Isabelle Perseil (INSERM)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- *Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)*
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*

- "Maddalena Fratelli" <maddalena@marionegri.it>
- "Christian Ohmann" <christianohmann@outlook.de>
- "Jonathan Tedds" <tedds@ebi.ac.uk>
- "paolo romano" <paolo.romano@hsanmartino.it>

Agenda

- Sprint 2

Copy of Tchat:

Vous 14:01

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPy-GIt1BJjhNM0-xKTnzCICQ5OFT077IhyeGkPc/edit#>

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPy-GIt1BJjhNM0-xKTnzCICQ5OFT077IhyeGkPc/edit#>

Vous à Tout le monde 14:22

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit#gid=0>

Vous à Isabelle Perseil (Message direct) 14:28

Tu as du recevoir un mail, je viens de te "taguer"

Vous à Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER) (Message direct) 14:32

Hi Mickael. Can you tell me were you want to add inputs? (You can add colors in the second sheet in the googlesheet (MR column)

Zia Rehman à Tout le monde 15:00

Sorry, I have to leave because of another meeting starting soon, see you next time.

Vous à Roland Pieruschka (Message direct) 15:02

I ve not asked to you sorry 😊 is all already fine for you, do you have found where your parts are?

Isabelle Perseil à Tout le monde 15:29

Bye everyone, see you in the next meeting on Friday

Emma Karoune à Tout le monde 15:32

sorry I have to go now - thanks all

jean-marie burel à Tout le monde 15:39

I have to go. See you on Friday

Michael Raess (INFRAFRONTIER) 15:39

Sorry, I also have to leave now

Meeting Paper sprint 1 SP#14 14/03/2023 9:00 CEST

Attendees: Please see below the active copy!

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**

- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**
- Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)
- **Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)**
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- Katrina Exter (EMBRC)
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Jing Tang (EATRIS)**
- Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)
- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**
- Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)
- Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)
- **Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)**
- Dario Longo (Euro-BioImaging Med-Hub, CNR)
- Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- **Rafaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- **Marzia Massini (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- **Ugis Sarkans (EGI)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- "Maddalena Fratelli" <maddalena@marionegri.it>
- "Christian Ohmann" <christianohmann@outlook.de>
- "Jonathan Tedds" <tedds@ebi.ac.uk>
- "Helen Parkinson" <parkinso@ebi.ac.uk>
- "paolo romano" <paolo.romano@hsanmartino.it>

Agenda

- Sprint 1

Notes

Our first radical collaboration paper sprint:

Zoom Réunion

Vous voyez actuellement l'écran de Phil Gribbon Options d'affichage

PAPER DRAFT Sustainability of FAIR Life Science Resources and Projects V2_13032023

Building your section - what main components are needed?

- easier to change and move around
- reword the text of others in suggestion mode, but focus today should be on new text

Building your section - what main components are needed?

- listing section related challenges, why are we doing this work in EOSC-LIFE and what do we seek to achieve?
- the overall focus should be on sustainability dimension - describe briefly sustainability components and relevant information, were these components designed at the outset or retrospectively applied?
- in the landscape, how is the component involved linked to or related to other parallel initiatives
- Add recommendation if any, concerning the topic or more globally how it should or shouldn't be implemented for sustainability aspect - this may eventually be moved to the conclusion section in the final version

Introduction

There is an increased demand from the life science communities to share and access high quality data resources in order to: i) enhance the value and understanding of internal results by extending analyses to include complementary or orthogonal data and; ii) provide the substrate of training data necessary to support non-hypothesis driven scientific discovery and advancement in clinical practice, using machine based methods; iii) share data to inform decision-making by policy makers (eg funders, politicians, industrial partners), in this

Participants (11)

Romain David - ERINHL (Hôte, moi) [Microphone icon]

Phil Gribbon (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Niklas Blomberg (Invité) [Microphone icon]

rafaelematteoni (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jean-Karim Heriche (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Alejandro Sanchez Pla (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jessica Klemieir (EMBL) (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jing Tang (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Kim Gurwitz (Invité) [Microphone icon]

marzia massimi (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Ugis Sarkans (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Fin

Taper ici pour rechercher

4°C Ensoleillé 09:07 14/03/2023

Zoom Réunion

Participants (12)

Romain David - ERINHL (Hôte, moi) [Microphone icon]

rafaelematteoni (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Niklas Blomberg (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Phil Gribbon (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Antonio Rosato (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Arina Rybina (Euro-Bioma... (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jean-Karim Heriche (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jessica Klemieir (EMBL) (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Jing Tang (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Kim Gurwitz (Invité) [Microphone icon]

marzia massimi (Invité) [Microphone icon]

Ugis Sarkans (Invité) [Microphone icon]

1

Inviter Désactiver tous les sons

Taper ici pour rechercher

4°C Ensoleillé 09:43 14/03/2023

...

Actions to be done

- ...
- #Copy of tchat
 - Phil Gribbon à Tout le monde 9:04
 - <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPY-Glt1BJjhNM0-xKTNzCICQ5OFT077lhYeGkPc/edit#>
 - Niklas Blomberg à Tout le monde 9:05
 - I have a call at 10am CET for 10-15 minutes but will get back
 - Vous à Tout le monde 9:05

please add also your name in the notes

Rolling notes:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

you can also add in notes remarks and suggestions to improve the method

Do not hesitate to use the tchat to exchange on ideas, possible rewording

Vous à Tout le monde 9:10

lessons learned and possible recommandations are the targets?

Ugis Sarkans à Vous (Message direct) 9:12

Romain, you are leading on figures, right? Shall I paste my ideas into the figures.ppt, after slide #13?

Jing Tang à Vous (Message direct) 9:12

Hi Romain, which task you have assigned to me? I could not find it in the google doc. My name is Jing Tang.

Vous à Ugis Sarkans (Message direct) 9:14

Thanks! yes I ll have a look and come back to you thanks!

Vous à Jing Tang (Message direct) 9:14

Hi! Tchecked! Your initials are TT

Ugis Sarkans à Vous (Message direct) 9:14

ok - give me 10 mins

Vous à Jing Tang (Message direct) 9:15

TT

Ugis Sarkans à Vous (Message direct) 9:32

Done - slides 14 and 15. Very rough at the moment.

Vous à Ugis Sarkans (Message direct) 9:38

That s Always rough as a first step :)

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 9:42

Good morning everyone, sorry I could not join earlier

Vous à Tout le monde 9:42

Don't mind overlapping at this stage 😊 just try to be original, but if it is repetitive, that will underline ideas we will keep as essentials

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Vous (Message direct) 9:43

Hi Romain - could you share the file we are currently looking at?

Vous à Tout le monde 9:45

16 points have to be restructured Indeed. We didn't erase anoone at this step anyone. But feel free to reorganise it (group certains)

Vous à Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) (Message direct) 9:46

Hi Arina!

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPy-GIt1BJjhNM0-xKTNzCICQ5OFT077lhYeGkPc/edit#>

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Vous (Message direct) 9:46

Many thanks!

Vous à Tout le monde 9:47

We will take a copy of the paper at each step (at least after each meeting)

Phil Gribbon à Tout le monde 9:51

Work on till 10:10 am AM CET. Then 10 min break and chat again at 10:20am

Kim Gurwitz à Tout le monde 9:53

I need to leave at 10:15 CET for another meeting. I'll continue working on my sections until then. I have also set aside time on Friday morning to work on this further with other colleagues before the weekly paper catch up at 13:00 CET, Friday 17th March

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 9:56

Similar here - I booked some time this week for working on text and figures.

Niklas Blomberg à Tout le monde 10:29

I need to briefly step out - will call back in

Pauline Audergon à Tout le monde 10:57

I apologise, I need to leave

Meeting SP#13 10/03/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)
- **Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)**
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**
- **Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)**
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**
- **Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)**
- Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jing Tang (EATRIS)
- Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)
- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**
- Rebecca Ludwig (EATRIS)
- Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)
- Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)
- Dario Longo (Euro-Biolmaging Med-Hub, CNR)
- Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)
- Raffaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR; now on travel)
- Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EMBL-EBI - can't join today, but working on a figure as discussed last week)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg) Dear Phil and Romain, dear all! Apologies as I unfortunately can not join the call today (collision with a Euro-BioImaging seminar) - I should however be able to attend the sprint on 14th March and join that call 10-11 CET (as my other meeting I had in the schedule before was shifted to 15th)

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - 1- add to the [figures ppt](#) the names of the sections that the figure should be for, so the figure creators can see what the scope of the content of the figures should be -> **to be Done and to be done in the paper Draft too**
 - 2- migrate all Sustainability paper doc to a dedicated shared folder in EOSC-LIFE Drive **DONE**
 - 3- create the draft in googledoc where anyone can contribute **DONE**: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SQ6GPy-Glt1BJjhNM0-xKTNzCICQ5OFT077lhyeGkPc/edit?usp=sharing>
 - journal: [EMBO journal](#) (Open Science) -> any new information?
- **Paper writing sprints organisation**

Notes

- First draft in place by 1st April
- Submission penciled in for end of April
- Please tag persons for each section in the Paper Draft document or if you need help from another partner
- Zoom room for paper sprint 14th March
<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81867144296?pwd=WjN4VytVanpRRW9lYkxoRUNuaEVIQT09>

ID recurrent meeting: 818 6714 4296

Code secret : 877000

- (PG to send out invites, Romain to set up Zoom booking)
- Main: - Session A Morning of the 14th March (9am to 11am)
 - Extra:- Session B Afternoon of the 14th March (2pm - 4pm)
-

Actions to be done

- Sprint
- Sprint meeting room creation **DONE**
- Figures call in the paper draft **DONE**

- Sections in the figure google slide **DONE**
- #Copy of tchat

...

Meeting template SP#12 03/03/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees:

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- *Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)*
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**
- *Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)*
- **Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)**
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- *Harald Wagener (CHARITE)*
- *Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)*
- *Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)*
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- *Jing Tang (EATRIS)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)*
- *Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)*
- *Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Dario Longo (Euro-BioImaging Med-Hub, CNR)*
- **Ugis Sarkans (EuBI, EMBL-EBI)**
- **Raffaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- **Emma Karoune - Alan Turing Institute/Historic England**
- **Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)**
- **Jessica Klemeier (EMBL)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- *Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee), Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI; on leave)*

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - Sara to add EOSC-Life design elements **DONE**

- Romain & Phil to draft a first figure before next sustainability paper meeting **DONE**
- Sara and colleagues to add Title, names, affiliations and others in the draft, the rolling notes and the paper management google sheet **REMINDER + 2 colleagues of Helen (Jessica and Rupert joining) Invites formr**
- ALL: first participation open -> @Phil can you send an email to the whole team for FIGURES?
- **Please take care of Figure implementation rules** (and add one if you want)
- https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1wXErGWUVtsXUS8bCtmgPAvJmBZQyU92MlqfbRqHcSc/edit#slide=id.g210cc4c1b03_0_40
- Paper sprint meetings organisation and leader nomination validation
 - Timing options:
 - Decision - 14th March
 - Sprint options (PG to send out invites, Romain to set up Zoom booking)
 - Main: - Session A Morning of the 14th March (9am to 11am)
 - Extra:- Session B Afternoon of the 14th March (2pm - 4pm)
 - Single clear Table of Contents needed in the paper (before 13th March)
 - Separate document for each section to be worked on by each section group.
 - After sprint - copy text into the main document
- Reminder of deadlines -> steps needed
 - Submission on May (or end of April)
- AOB?
- Another idea for journal: [EMBO journal](#) (Open Science), some previous interaction as through this publication: [ELIXIR-EXCELERATE: establishing Europe's data infrastructure for the life science research of the future](#)
<https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/emboj.2020107409>

Notes

PG reached out to journal chief editor. Awaiting response:

Dear Kazuhiko Takeuchi,

I would like to enquire about a submission to the journal "Sustainability Science" and which would be the optimal category. The work we would intend to submit will describe the resources and services which have been supported and/or created within the EOSC-LIFE project.....

The specific question relates to the type of publication you see this topic falling under. Would it be possible for this work to be an invited "Overview article" as it covers general

themes related to life science resource sustainability, or do you see it more as a "Case Report" format?

RESPONSE:

Good day!

From your explanation, it fits either as an overview or technical report regarding the article category.

However, this does not imply that the paper will be accepted or forwarded for review. The editors will check the scope of the paper and decide.

Thank you for your understanding, have a nice day!

Warm regards,

Editorial Assistant

...

Actions to be done

...

1- add to the [figures ppt](#) the names of the sections that the figure should be for, so the figure creators can see what the scope of the content of the figures should be

#Copy of tchat

Phil Gribbon 13:01

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

Phil Gribbon à Tout le monde 13:06

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit#gid=2117890693>

Vous à Tout le monde 13:09

please add your name and affiliation in bold in the present list

Emma Karoune à Tout le monde 13:16

apologies I have joined late but my last meeting over ran

Vous à Tout le monde 13:19

Hi Emma thanks to join

@Emma do you want to introduce yourself?

From my side, figures often help me to better formulate and clarify ideas :)

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:21

For me too - Figures tell a lot

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) à Tout le monde 13:23

The Google Slides can be used for initial idea collection and drafting of figures. Final figure creation will need to use different program to ensure appropriate resolution and flexibility of editing the image.

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:23

Exactly.

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) à Tout le monde 13:25

It would probably be useful to create one Google Drive folder and make it possible for authors to upload specific images that will be used in their figure (Name: SectionName_ImageName/Number, for example). These can then be more easily important into different graphic design programs to create final figures.

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:25

There should be no problem exporting the objects into different software

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:27

Hello Emma 😊

Philipp Gormanns à Tout le monde 13:27

Sorry I have to leave for another meeting. I'll catch up via the minutes. See you

Vous à Tout le monde 13:27

@Arina: do you want to introduce Emma?

@Philipp: can you update your affiliations info on the draft?

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Vous (Message direct) 13:28

Yes, sure

Waiting for the moment!

Vous à Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) (Message direct) 13:31

:)

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Vous (Message direct) 13:33

Team work!

Vous à Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) (Message direct) 13:34

yes, I love that

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Vous (Message direct) 13:34

👍

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:35

In the week 13-18 March?

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:37

I'll only have time Wed 15 or Fri 17 March.

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:37

ISIDORe AGM 28-30 March

Wed 15 sounds good

katrina à Tout le monde 13:40

I have given myself the 13 to work on this. 14 and 15 I am in a meeting

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:40

Morning 14 unfortunately does not work for me

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:40

Tuesday 14 in the morning can work for me.

Antonio Rosato à Tout le monde 13:40

the morning of the 14th would be ok for me

katrina à Tout le monde 13:41

if we can have the google drive place and one document in there for each section, then those of us who cannot make it can start writing in the appropriate place

rafaelematteoni à Tout le monde 13:41

14 any time fine with me...

Vous à Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) (Message direct) 13:55

Can you zoom in?

Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging) à Tout le monde 13:58

<https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/emj.2020107409>

Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC) 13:58

I have created a folder in our EOSC-Life Google Drive and provided Phil and Romain with Editor rights.

Meeting template SP#11 23/02/2023 12:00 CEST

Attendees:

Phil, Sara, Romain

Agenda

- Figure team strategy

Notes

Figure strategy

- Sara to identify key design elements from EOSC google drive
- RB and PG will prepare an initial overview figure for next meeting in the doc above
- Sprint sessions for figure production will be possible
- Shorthand as a tool for broader dissemination support
- Integrate 2-D /QR barcodes included in the figures to enhance reuse
- Need figure legends defined as starting point (link text and figure and vice-versa)
- Future call on dissemination plan - big impact on eventual citation rates

Actions to be done

Sara to add EOSC-Life design elements

Romain & Phil to draft a first figure before next sustainability paper meeting

Sara and colleagues to add Title, names, affiliations and others in the draft, the rolling notes and the paper management google sheet

ALL: first participation open -> @Phil can you send an email to the whole team?

Please take care of Figure implementation rules (and add one if you want)

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1wXErGWUVtsXUS8bCtmgPAvJmBZQyU92MlgfbRqHcScc/edit#slide=id.g210cc4c1b03_0_40

Meeting SP#10 17/02/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees (Bold):

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI)**

- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**
- **Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)**
- **Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)**
- Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**
- Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- **Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)**
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jing Tang (EATRIS)
- **Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)**
- Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)
- Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)
- Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)
- Dario Longo (Euro-BioImaging Med-Hub, CNR)
- Sara Crockett (BBMRI-ERIC)
- **Raffaele Matteoni (INFRAFRONTIER, CNR)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

Apologized:

- Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
-

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - **ROMAIN** to translate topics involvements in the googlesheet
 - **ALL** to validate and complete the plan and involvements in the google sheet
 - **ALL** to check affiliations and ORCID's for Authors
- Other topics missing
- Peoples without involvements / parts without involvements
- Schedule for the paper and deadline submission on **end of April -> GANT graph?**
- **Paper sprint and leaders nomination per part**
- AOB

Notes

Include **BY-COVID** activities within the conclusions (WP11 - 13)

Actions to be done

Romain and Phil G to prepare a "to-do" list for section leaders.

email / contact to WP3 for the open call methodology related contents

Add sections to the draft

PG - to contact editors of "Sustainability Science" to check on relevance and opportunities for submission...

PG Emails to WP6 and FAIRsharing to conform contributions (see spreadsheet)

Deadline for submission 31st April (need to cover publication costs from the EOSC-LIFE budget)

Sprint 1 w/c 20th Feb (RD will propose to each leader @ next call on 3rd March)

...

Meeting template SP#9 10/02/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees (Bold):

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**
- **Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)**
- *Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)*
- *Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)*
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- **Katrina Exter (EMBRC)**
- **Harald Wagener (CHARITE)**
- **Susanna Sansone (ELIXIR, Oxford)**
- *Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)*
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)*
- *Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)*
- *Jing Tang (EATRIS)*
- *Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)*
- *Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)*
- *Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)*
- *Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)*
- *Antonio Rosato (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)*
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

, ...

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - Romain to ordonate topics for a plan for discussion (**DONE**), Helen to do the first review on it, **DONE** All to add topics / your name on a topic

- Romain to complete the name list and cross validate affiliations / participation / mailto list and list of authors (partially **DONE**)
- Phil to send an email with ordonate list of topics to request through Niklas and Friederike last suggestions to the whole EOSC-Life community (**Done**)
- **ALL** to validate categories in the googlesheet (leaded by Jean-Karim)
- BJ response for paper format and editor requirements
- Validation of the plan
- Next step:
 - email with link to the topics (in another doc?)
 - to tag peoples in the paper -
 - paper sprint
- Submission in May
- How many words? -> 3000 to be distributed for each topic “distribution plan”

Proposal for ideas organization (and assignment for a paper sprint)

FIRST GENERAL COMMENT: sometimes focusing on the process and less so on outcomes/impact. If each section can deliver at least one recommendation would be great

TODO: insert figure in drafting links

1) Sustainability issues related to data sharing in international scientific projects:

a) General considerations

- i) EOSC-Life sustainability Overall project presentation; long-term sustainability; context (**NBI**)
- ii) Positioning of EOSC-LIFE within the wider EOSC ecosystem (**NBI**)
- iii) How EOSCLife is organized - how that achieves impact - may cover - Project management issues and key stones (**PA?**)
- iv) Open science contribution to sustainability - hard to sustain closed products, risks of sustainability in open science - reliance on freeware etc (**HP**)
- v) Vocabularies and other FAIR principles related sustainability challenges (All... in particular: RD, JT, HP, HH)
- vi) Data access and data sharing governance (RD, JWB, **XX?**)

b) Case studies

Intro to case studies, breadth, depth, state of maturity. Where longer documentation exists (e.g. our internal documents looking at the sustainability of these projects), give link to those

- i) WP3 (**PA, ARy, ARo, PGo**) - Short Questionnaire of 5-6 questions to highlight challenges / main issues in EOSC-Life Cases Studies (**PA - RD**)
 - (1) What did EOSC-life enable the projects to achieve? as Vignettes? **XX (HW)**
 - (2) Phytolith project (**JMB - HH - EK - ARy**)

- (3) *Galaxy-commercial (Berenice project) (CP - JK- ARy)*
Reflexion of differents aspects
- (4) *QSM4SENIOR (Alexandre Vignaud project): (Link to Industry plus request to Cloud Resources through EOSC-Life - challenge to ensure sustainability after project runs out?) - (CP- AR - PA-JMB) Reflexion of differents aspects*
- (5) *The EMBRC bioinformatics pipeline (MetaGOflow) (KE)*
- (6) *cross-RI project integrated data sets (PGo)*
Consider if visually attractive image / diagram which could be included / provided by the Demonstrator team(s) - (ARy)

ii) *Scientific impact on wider community and changes occurring in working practice (usage level and metrics on resource utilization, if available) (PGr, MF)*

- (1) *Example of the consultation process during the open calls < 20% of projects funded but substantial benefit to the applicants*
 - (a) *Dearth of experts to provide practical guidance + training to the applicants and also implemented projects*
 - (b) *sustainability recommendation - build a pool of experts for future sustainability.*
 - (c) *...*
- (2) *Covid 19 portal example. EOSC-Life WP14 products (toolbox for sensitive data, clinical research repository) ML->LM?, XX*

2) **Key Components for FAIR sharing sustainability**

a. **Community components: “humans and data” (XX)**

i. *Cross-RI working and improving interoperability - Sustainability of network/community (PA - RD?, RP, KTG, RL, PGo)*

- 1. **JKH:**
 - a. *several RI wrote white papers. Possible paths for sustainability*
 - b. *Sustainability checklist for e.g. capacity, data*
- 2. **RP:**
 - a. *Links to tools within the INFRA-SERV /INFRA-TECH/ INFRA-EOSC projects: EOSC-Life as a nucleus for development of data management tools now reused in new projects and grant applications*
- 3. *Example of EU-OS: INSTRUCT and EU-OS:Eurobiomaging MoU's and joint (experimental focussed) projects which emerged subsequently*
- 4. *Served as a nucleus of future project co-operations between RI communities in InfraServe and other instruments*
- 5. **CG:**
BiOcean5D, BlueRemediomics, BlueCloudII and MICROBE leverage aspects of data management, processing and provenance, established as part of this ELIXIR community and the platforms, and help deliver ELIXIR aims. For example, the

ESOC-life demonstrator implemented a lightweight version of the MGNify pipeline, MetaGOFlow. Using ELIXIR platform solutions, we are working on importing MetaGOFlow RO-Crates as a means of federating analyses (see also report below)

- **ARy:**
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1byZeFeI5qMCCe-aW1YKzy4yyAfnkKyMf9zwX4Fvuw1Y/edit#> **ARy**
 - Key points to mention: Access to experts and training (involving expert) See also <https://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/training-schools/neubias-academy-home/defragmentation-training-school-2022/> 2023 upcoming focusing on Infrastructures and Data Management. (May 2023) Another example EBI imaging courses (involving experts too)
 - Phytolith project: 2 upcoming workshops (May/June 2023) involving experts

ii. **Data gathering process, outcomes and impact for sustainability assessment of Demonstrator generated workflows and data resources** (across starting set of demonstrators and the 3 subsequent calls) (KE, **JMB**, **PGo**, **XX**)

1. Define information to be captured
2. Align with the WP3 survey process (minimize spamming of projects)
3. Recognise that some demonstrators may not be able provide info (closed some time ago)
4. What about WP7 services? Is this something to be sustained beyond the project or only as support for the demonstrators? (**LDC**)
5. WP2 roadmap sustainability, data access for workflows and tools **JKH**

iii. **Sustainable training and training on FAIR implementation and support of EOSC-Life activities** with training through the project e.g. workshops, training open calls (KTG, RL)

1. "-proposed short section on sustainable training and training on FAIR implementation - content, delivery, capacity strengthening. FAIR and open science start with FAIR and open training - training is a crucial vehicle for cultural change. support of EOSC-Life activities with training through the project e.g. workshops, training open calls -sustainable network and community (and how this is supported through training)"

b. Technical milestones (to be reworded **XX - DLL**)

- i. Sustainability: list of assets
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1WKJLF8eRY_KK4V-KbzFezQdt7PQPzMnIW4uHbBKQbAA/edit#gid=0 **LDC**
- ii. sustainability of sharing and shared (meta)data (**KE**)

- iii. Ensuring legal and policy requirements are traceable from data (as this allows for sustainability) (KE)
- iv. Ensuring traceability (provenance) for useful sustainability (KE)
- v. Cross RI data harmonization and analyses in terms of impact of EOSC-LIFE (PG)
- vi. WP1: Curation of FAIR data resources, WP1,3: Data curation in support of Demonstrators and Open Calls (RM - MM)
- vii. Software sustainability - Distinction should be made between data and SW sustainability - there are different challenges (HP)
- viii. Workflows - Provenance and Reproducibility sustainability challenges (? CG, ARo, JJ, ASP, PH)
- ix. Sensitive data Challenges (RD, ...)
 - 1. WP4 Toolbox sustainability (RD - JWB - CO - ML)
 - 2. Toolbox adoption issues
 - 3. Risk overviews through sustainability (RD)
- x. Jonathan: LS service sustainability in relation to WP5 - AAI (JT)
 - 1. Ludek: common services crossing drastically different stakeholders and funders. Easy under ELIXIR RI - to start ELIXIR-AAI. Under LS-AAI and cross-RI, very different experiences and useful contributions. Service running and governance aspects (LM)
 - 2. clarity when you go beyond single institute / beyond single RI.
- xi. Role of commercial cloud providers in sustainability - (XX)
 - 1. differences between the US and EU experiences
 - 2. linked to skills and capabilities to actually design/setup and implement
- xii. FAIRsharing Collection and links to EOSC - (XX)
- xiii. Data feeds (how data are served) - (XX)

3) **Lessons learned for FAIR data sharing sustainability**

- a. Community components
 - i. Inter RIs challenges prioritization - (XX)
 - ii. focus on training impacts (RD, CG, ...)
- b. Technical implementations XX
- c. Other (to be reworded)
 - i. Reliance on commercial entities for core EOSC services XX
 - ii. How best practices are or are not adaptable (between RIs) XX
 - iii. Risks mitigation and sharing with risk mitigation in the long term (RD, XX)
 - iv. Recommendations (HP, XX)
 - 1. Each inf. has a sustainability strategy
 - 2. Each service has a strategy - based on whether it is a life si general or domain specific strategy
 - 3. Something re:lifecycle of services and infs.
 - 4. Sustainability needs to be built in, not added at the end (HP)
 - 5. Funding/Sustainability of shared/common services like AAI or multi-cloud capacity provisioning (LM)

Conclusion

- a. Importance of funding as a keystone of sustainability **XX** (there are other components, nuance, usage, complexity, incentivization of sustainability - research drivers don't promote this for example **HP**)
- b. Top 5 or 10 recommendations / take home message (**ALL**)

Notes

Journal choice:

Nature Biotech B have declined the manuscript

"While it can be difficult to determine the editorial suitability of a manuscript from the limited information contained in presubmission inquiries, I feel that the manuscript you describe will be more appropriately presented in another journal, such as Genome Biology".

<https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/aims-and-scope>

- Planned figures - use shared google slides (Folder + links here)
 - Overview figure of the EOSC-LIFE "Vision" or re-use the WP2 roadmap **link here (JK)**
 - EOSC-LIFE call for projects - overview of project scientific domains /subjects /outputs/resources-generated/interactions and what was created, eg., workflows, (**RD**)
 - maturity analysis + where resources (software and data) sit in the sustainability life-cycle (Helen) - earlier figures from WP1 describing the domain -
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1dqcuajeUf_slwWwC_6p6-wXZ7rj8_9qqOn2l-mE/edit#slide=id.p2 - see slide 3 for re-usable icons
 - Audience/Users of EOSC-LIFE resources: where does it sit in the overall ecosystem (cf FAIRsharing, OPEN AIRE etc), (Arina - Romain)
 - Figure to accompany a section on lessons learned from EOSC Life: what is important for having FAIR resources, projects, workflows, processed, portals (etc) to be sustainable. (**KE**)
 - Sustainability of actions undertaken to make scientific outputs and software FAIR
 - Conversely, how making these digital objects FAIR, makes them sustainable resources
 - Role of legal / permits in sustainability (it does not make things sustainable but it is necessary to be FAIR managed in order for the related resources to be sustainably available
 - Role of provenance (and licences) in sustainability
 - Impact of (local, regional, european) policies on sustainability
 - KE: I really don't see this point as being part of a figure: also of the community as for the knowledge we have built in EOSC-Life and the people we have brought

together - how do we maintain this once the project ends? **SAS, AL**
Put in place by governance in several disciplines (e.g. also a small paragraph on it)

...

Actions to be done

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Meeting SP#8 03/02/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees (Bold):

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)
- **Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)**
- **Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)**
- **Philipp Gormanns (INFRAFRONTIER)**
- Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)
- Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- Katrina Exter (EMBRC)
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- **Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)**
- Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)
- Jing Tang (EATRIS)
- Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)
- **Kim Gurwitz (EMBL-EBI)**
- **Jose Miguel Lopez-Coronado (MIRRI)**
- Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)
- Antonio Rosato (Instruct-ERIC)
- **Helen Parkinson (EMBL-EBI)**
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO LIST ABOVE and in the Paper draft with complete affiliations!!**

, ...

Agenda

- "Topics plan" in the Goolesheet

- <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZlUCUwg oY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit?usp=sharing>
- Other points to be added
- Order in the plan
- Other willingness to participate
- Planned figures - use shared google slides (Folder + links here)
 - Overview figure of the EOSC-LIFE "Vision" or re-use the WP2 roadmap **link here (JK)**
 - EOSC-LIFE call for projects - overview of project scientific domains /subjects /outputs/resources-generated/interactions and what was created, eg., workflows, (Romain)
 - maturity analysis + where resources (software and data) sit in the sustainability life-cycle (Helen) - earlier figures from WP1 describing the domain -
<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1dqcuajeUf- slwlvWi C 6p6-wXZ7rj8 9qqOn2l-mE/edit#slide=id.p2> - see slide 3 for re-usable icons
 - Audience/Users of EOSC-LIFE resources: where does it sit in the overall ecosystem (cf FAIRsharing, OPEN AIRE etc), (Arina - Romain)
 - Sustainability in a more general sens more relevant? Focus on generalizing recommendations and lessons learned (KE)
 - of data
 - legal / permit the collection of material
- Exchanges with NB editors (NB, PG)
 - From Nature Biotechnology Researchers may request informal feedback from the editors on whether a potential manuscript may be appropriate for the journal. Presubmission inquiries are optional and should not be used to submit a full manuscript. If your manuscript is already written please proceed with a full formal submission. For a presubmission inquiry you may either submit summary files or enter pertinent information in the "Abstract" and "Manuscript Comment" text boxes. To expedite the process, it is not necessary to provide details of contributing authors. If you are invited to submit a full manuscript, the e-mail conveying our invitation will contain a link that will allow you to submit the manuscript files and other required information under the same tracking number.

Title: Achieving sustainability for life science data resources, workflows and software: lessons from the European Open Science Cloud

Abstract sent to NB:

There is an increased demand from the life science communities to share and access high quality data resources in order to: i) enhance the value and understanding of internal results by extending analyses to include complementary or orthogonal data and; ii) provide the substrate of training data necessary to support non-hypothesis driven scientific discovery and advancement in clinical practice, using machine-based methods; and iii) share data to inform decision-making by policy makers. Using the experience gained from the wide-ranging European Open Science Cloud project, EOSC-LIFE (<https://www.eosc-life.eu/>), we describe the special considerations necessary to meet the challenges of ensuring long term sustainable reuse of life science data resources, and workflow tools, in an increasingly open science world where data and software are shared and widely accessible. Financial challenges arise due to the increasing level of data and services being generated across the communities, as well as technical challenges related to the need for effective widespread implementation of FAIR components including identifiers, metadata schemata, vocabularies and provenance which are inconsistently applied and act as a brake on interoperability and reuse opportunities. Finally, organisational challenges arise from non-aligned impact and reward mechanisms within academic organisations whereby novelty and quickly following new trends leads to funding or tenure extensions, rather than focussing on the sustainability of existing resources. The publication will be illustrated by highlights from relevant use cases showing the interactions between users and services and resources and their approach to sustainability.

Your manuscript submission has been assigned the following tracking number: NBT-PI59041. Please quote this number in any correspondence with the editorial office.

-
- AOB

Notes

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Actions to be done

...

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Meeting template SP#7 27/01/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees (Bold):

- **Romain David (ERINHA),**
- **Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)**
- **Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)**
- **Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)**
- **Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)**
- **Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)**
- **Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)**
- *Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)*
- *Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)*
- *Katrina Exter (EMBRC)*
- **Harald Wagener (CHARITE)**
- **Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)**
- *Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR)*
- *Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)*
- **Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)**
- **Jing Tang (EATRIS)**
- **Maddalena Fratelli (EATRIS)**
- ...
- Add your name and affiliation and **PLEASE ADD YOURSELF IN THE MAILTO ABOVE!!**

Agenda

- Point to be added to the agenda?
- To be validated
 - Journal choice discussion #2
 - All people contributed? Based on already done -> First choice targeting policy makers
 - Order:
 - Nature Biotech (Phil: FAIRsharing was published in that journal) (3000 words)
 - Scientific Data: FAIR principles/software papers published (3000 words)
 - Sustainability Science Option for more words
 - Participations rules ()
 - RD: Propose to put rules at the end of each email.
 - Phil: +1
 - Editorial group: JKH, JMB, PG, RD, NB ... other?
 - initial group below. Feel free to join if possible/available Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee), Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL), Phil Gribbon (EU-OS), Romain David (ERINHA), Niklas Bloomberg (ELIXIR)
 -

- *Key points topics for the core discussion (please add initials where you want to contribute)*
 - *WP4 Toolbox sustainability (RD - JWB - CO)*
 - *Software sustainability -*
 - *Distinction should be made between data and SW sustainability - there are different challenges (HP)*
 - *If this is considered useful: Sustainability of Models and the connected data (experimental, kinetic constants) (HVW)*
 - *Workflows - Provenance and Reproducibility sustainability challenges (? CG, ARo, IP, ASP)*
 - *WP3 (PA, AR, PGo) - Short Questionnaire of 5-6 questions to highlight challenges / main issues in EOSC-Life Cases Studies (PA - RD)*
 - *What did EOSC-life enable the projects to achieve? as Vignettes?*
 - *Phytolith project (JMB - HH - EK - AR)*
 - *Galaxy-commercial (Berenice project)*
 - *cross-RI project integrated data sets (PGo)*
 - *Consider if visually attractive image / diagram which could be included / provided by the Demonstrator team(s) - Arina*
 - *positioning of EOSC-LIFE within the wider EOSC ecosystem (NB)*
 - *open science contribution to sustainability - hard to sustain closed products, risks of sustainability in open science -reliance on freeware etc (HP)*
 - *Sensitive data Challenges (RD, ...)*
 - *Vocabularies and other FAIR principles related challenges (All... in particular: RD, JT)*
 - *Project management issues and key stones (PA?)*
 - *Sustainable training and training on FAIR implementation and support of EOSC-Life activities with training through the project e.g. workshops, training open calls (KTG, RL)*
 - *Cross-RI working and improving interoperability - Sustainability of network/community (PA - RD?, RP, KTG, RL, PGo)*
 - *JKH:*
 - *several RI wrote white papers. Possible paths for sustainability*
 - *Community of devs, etc. Did not come up with anything concrete. Required leaders/efforts to coordinate*
 - *RP:*
 - *Links to tools within the INFRA-SERV /INFRA-TECH/ INFRA-EOSC projects: EOSC-Life as a nucleus for development of data management tools now reused in new projects and grant applications*
 - *Example of EU-OS: INSTRUCT and EU-OS:Eurobiomaging MoU's and joint (experimental focussed) projects which emerged subsequently*
 - *Served as a nucleus of future project co-operations between RI communities in InfraServe and other instruments*
 - *CG:*

BiOcean5D, BlueRemediomics, BlueCloudII and MICROBE leverage aspects of data management, processing and provenance, established as part of this ELIXIR community and the platforms, and help deliver ELIXIR aims. For example, the ESOC-life demonstrator implemented a lightweight version of the MGNify pipeline, MetaGOFlow. Using ELIXIR platform solutions, we are working on importing MetaGOFlow RO-Crates as a means of federating analyses (see also report below)

- AR:
 - <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1byZeFeI5qMCCe-aW1YKzy4yyAfnkKyMf9zwX4Fvuw1Y/edit#>
 - Key points to mention: Access to experts and training (involving expert) See also <https://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/training-schools/neubias-academy-home/defragmentation-training-school-2022/> 2023 upcoming focusing on Infrastructures and Data Management. (May 2023) Another example EBI imaging courses (involving experts too)
 - Phytolith project: 2 upcoming workshops (May/June 2023) involving experts
- Added Friday after WP5 meeting:
 - Jonathan: LS service sustainability in relation to WP5
 - Ludek: common services crossing drastically different stakeholders and funders. Easy under ELIXIR RI - to start ELIXIR-AAI. Under LS-AAI and cross-RI, very different experience and useful contribution. Service running and governance aspects - clarity when you go beyond single institute / beyond single RI.
- Scientific impact on wider community and changes occurring in working practice (usage level and metrics on resource utilization, if available) (PG, MF)
 - Example of the consultation process during the open calls < 20% of projects funded but substantial benefit to the applicants
 - Dearth of experts to provide practical guidance + training to the applicants and also implemented projects
 - Covid 19 portal example.
- Summarizing lessons learnt, especially training impacts (RD, CG, ...)
- **First point of next meeting** Data gathering process for sustainability assessment of Demonstrator generated workflows and data resources (across starting set of demonstrators and the 3 subsequent calls)
 - Define information to be captured
 - Align with the WP3 survey process (minimise spamming of projects)

- Recognise that some demonstrators may not be able provide info (closed some time ago)
- Align with Katrina Exter's existing summary (add link here)
 - [MetaGOFlow](#) (KE)
- Next meeting objectives ... AOB?

Notes (thanks to all to participate and add your Ideas)

In the agenda part!

Actions to be done

- 1) Circulate the main topics list to everyone (for those not present)
- 2) Contact Nat Biotech Journal (ask Niklas) to conform the suitability of the proposed manuscript
- 3) Add short impactful content against your names (All)
- 4) First illustration content/topic proposal (Arina)

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Vous 13:01

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit#

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pL4EPp2un6qeFI12pd43or5qP6m5BKprW3LPhAcPEjk/edit#>

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit#gid=519164427>

Carole Goble à Tout le monde 13:24

I am here!

I arrived late

Vignettes?

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:30

Sorry lost connection

Jean-Karim Heriche à Tout le monde 13:30

Me too. There's an EMBL-wide Zoom connection issue.

Carole Goble à Tout le monde 13:37

BiOcean5D, BlueRemediomics, BlueCloudII and MICROBE leverage aspects of data management, processing and provenance, established as part of this ELIXIR community and the platforms, and help deliver ELIXIR aims. For example, the ESOC-life demonstrator implemented a lightweight version of the MGnify pipeline, MetaGOFlow. Using ELIXIR platform solutions, we are working on importing MetaGOFlow RO-Crates as a means of federating analyses.

Vous à Tout le monde 13:38

the Rolling notes

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit

Arina Rybina (Euro-Biolmaging) à Tout le monde 13:40

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1byZeFeI5qMCCe-aW1YKzy4yyAfnkKyMf9zwX4Fvuw1Y/edit#>

Vous à Tout le monde 13:42

@Arina Nice peace of work!!

Carole Goble à Tout le monde 13:43

what about the defrag bioimaging hackathons too?

jean-marie burel à Tout le monde 13:45

<https://eubias.org/NEUBIAS/training-schools/neubias-academy-home/defragmentation-training-school-2022/>

Jean-Karim Heriche 13:59

I need to go to the next meeting. Bye. Have a good week-end.

Meeting template SP#6 20/01/2023 13:00 CEST

Attendees (13):

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)
- Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)
- Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)
- Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)
- Roland Pieruschka (EMPHASIS)
- Pauline Audergon (Instruct-ERIC)
- Christian Ohmann (ECRIN)
- Katrina Exter (EMBRC)
- Harald Wagener (CHARITE)
- Carole Goble (ELIXIR/ISBE/University of Manchester)
- Niklas Bloomberg (ELIXIR)

Agenda

- Paper content organisation: use-case centric/driven vs selecting use-cases that fit/illustrate the content → implication: select use cases first vs define content first
- Actions decided last meeting
 - Journal choice discussion
- Involvement of each for what

Notes

- Phil: present proposed structure of paper to group ~850 words at the moment
 - Katrina:
 - Importance to share is as important as to access
 - importance for Policy makers (to be expanded). especially for environmental data (climate change)
 - Carole
 - <https://future-of-research-software.org/draft-amsterdam-declaration-on-funding-research-software-sustainability/>
 - <https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010627>
 - Point also raised during the last UK-bioimaging working group. Strategy in place to reproduce the output

- *Pauline:*
 - *Sustainability of network/community? maybe to be considered (depends on space)*
 - *Need to underline human practices for sustainability in projects and time for be able to work with partners*
- *Niklas:*
 - *thought about network/community but decided to omit? Could be a strategy*
- *Romain: 3000 to 8000 words*
 - *Possible journals to [consider](#)*
 - *Phil: preference 5000+*
 - *Carole:*
 - *Scientific Data : ‘Comment’ is a flexible format used to publish short commentaries or opinions on research data policy, workflows or infrastructure that don't need to report a specific technology or finding. Comments are generally 1-5 pages in length. They may include one figure, table or box, and up to 25 references, however these formats are flexible. Comments should begin with a bolded “standfirst” of one or two sentences that reads smoothly with the rest of the piece. They may not include supplementary information, and generally do not have separate abstracts or author contributions statement. They are required to include a competing interests statement. An acknowledgements section is optional.*
 - *J-K: Preference for one single paper / no supplementary materials. So content can be indexed. Open access*
 - *Carole: main aim of paper*
 - *Influence vs EOSC story.*
 - *preference: use EOSC as a case study so it is read by policy makers*
 - *Romain: target policy makers and offer guidelines to people starting new FAIR journey*
 - *Niklas: Policy makers: like short papers with strong headers.*
 - *Katrina: hit policy makers is essential*
 - *J-K: start long (keep for final report) => shorter (hard)*
 - *Carole: hard to do. We will have to do 2 papers i.e. shortening a long paper does not really work.*
- *Participations rules*
 - <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluC-UwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit#gid=1514342247>
 - *Phil:*
 - *Rules coming from schema?*
 - *Romain: rules based on experience (creative commons license)*
 - *Keep timing rule is missing*
 - *Pauline:*
 - *involvement of Projects. Targeted projects?*

- Romain: people can join at any point as long as they bring something
- Carole: ask for specific/need to be clear on what is needed. To be content from targeted projects: need to give them a structured framework.
- FYI J-M/Henriette: Example and case study we met with Emma Karoune (Phytolith project). Happy to be involved
- Carole:
 - happy to contribute. Other people involved in other papers.
 - people involved in grant writing.
 - Limited bandwidth
- Romain:
 - the deadline is June so a bit of time.
- Niklas:
 - ask people for a list of bullet points during the first phase to allow for a first draft
- Romain:
 - Meeting next week 1pm CET

Actions to be done

All:

- Initials in Journal preference **(Not to late!)**
- Participations rules to be completed before adoption next meeting
- First adds with 2 or 3 sentences in the paper

Editorial group with JK, JM, PG, RD ... and CG? still open to other contribution

- Policy makers as a first target for the journal: to be validated and included in the rationale

#Copy of tchat

I ve forgotten to copy it sorry... content lost 😞 Please add missing content in the notes above!

Meeting SP#5 13/01/2023 13:00 CEST

!!Please add you and colleagues in the mailto list above

Attendees (8):

- Romain David (ERINHA),
- Phil Gribbon (EU-OS)
- Jean-Karim Heriche (EMBL)
- Antonio Rosato (INSTRUCT)
- Jean-Marie BUREL (EuroBio/University of Dundee)
- Jan-Willem Boiten (Lygature / EATRIS)
- Henriette HARMSE (EMBL-EBI)
- Arina Rybina (Euro-BioImaging Bio-Hub, WP3 co-lead, EMBL Heidelberg)

Agenda

- Actions decided last meeting
 - Rationales to be reordered / reworded: **Phil (see in the paper outline)**
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pL4EPp2un6qeFI12pd43or5qP6m5BKprW3LPhAcPEjk/edit#>
 - Open call projects features : to be populated by **Jean-Karim DONE**
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit?usp=sharing>
 - Journals descriptions : to be completed by **Romain DONE any other suggestion?**
 - Advice and opinions about journals: **All RD:DONE**
 - Rules of participation to be effective (5-10 lines): proposal from **Romain Done**, adds from **Phil and Jean-Karim**
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pGR65N-6GKDvh25fuZluCUwgoY78ywmR6hHe62hvrhk/edit?usp=sharing>
 - Create rolling notes for the paper meetings (**Romain**) **DONE**
https://docs.google.com/document/d/15XZXBg7YZTGxaUFcX1yi0Nmkc6vImM3pSxFbwOoTx_U/edit?usp=sharing
 - Mail from Friedericke and Niklas to the whole EOSC-Life community (**Phil**) after the call today **DONE**
- possible set of Journal and objective of the paper
- possible plan to be proposed
- Leaders for parts?
- Moving meeting time?

Notes

- The starting assumption was that people would know what training they would need but in practice, people are not generally aware of the technologies to implement their objectives and so don't know what training they need until after they've talked to experts.
- Workshop organised in december in 2021 to show the what was available from various experts in terms of knowledge and training. Open call reached out later on (at times > 1 year after.)
 - Phytolith project as good example
 - J-M: meeting with Emma Karone next week regarding training.
- WP2 use case: Food-born pathogens?
- One possible cross-RI demonstrator from WP3: "Integrating Eu-RI data sets for preclinical and discovery research bioimaging" (Euro-BioImaging/Eu-OS/Infrafrontier).
- **Actions to be done**
 - Ideas for draft questions for the survey on sustainability (use openAIRE examples?).
 - Understand how Dems are linked to existing tools (to be discussed next week)
 - Complete the rules
 - Identify 3 or 4 demonstrators which will be highlighted in the paper on diverse topics

- *Industry:*
academiahttps://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1gtYHK_kzbypQ8ocNCH6wjaO4cVIET4Mf
- *workflow focussed*
- *Cross-RI working and improving interoperability*
- *Privacy / Personal data*
- *Significant enhancement to a pre-existing resource managed by an RI*

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Meeting SP#4 07/01/2023 13:00 CEST

Planning for call 13th

- *Selection on possible set of Journal, (or at least alignment with Objectives of the paper), Consideration around the number of words - do not want to restrict ourselves - who do we want to target? - Open Access essential*
- *Identify target audience(s)*
 - *Providers of cloud resources and services*
 - *funders and institutional management functions*
 - *additional communities outside of the biology community*
- *Rules/ procedures for providing input to the paper*
 - *Trying to be representative for EOSC-Life (ideally participants from each WPs and each RIs*

ACTIONS before 13th

- *Rationales to be reordered / reworded: **Phil (see below)***
- *Open call projects features : to be populated by **Jean-Karim***
- *Journals descriptions : to be completed by **Romain***
- *Advice and opinions about journals: **All***
- *Rules of participation to be effective (5-10 lines): proposal from **Romain**, adds from **Phil and Jean-Karim***
- *Create rolling notes for the paper meetings (**Romain**)*
- *Mail from Friedericke and Niklas to the whole EOSC-Life community (**Phil**) after the call today*

#Copy of tchat 07/01

Totally in line with lessons learned

(and trying to discuss solutions)

reusing data and making them attractive

JK, have I forgotten something?

Meeting SP#3 16/12/2022 13:00 CEST

First brainstorming with 10-15 volunteers on scientific questions - Editorial team construction

- Task leader proposal - Journal options

We discussed on teasers in 2 phase for the paper (1 by Phil soon -> today or beginning of next week , 1 by Niklas), the rules of engagement (with repetitive invitation) and participating

method (in the text more than comments), and scheduled the next meeting, same zoom link for friday 6th of january, same time (13 CEST)

We will fix the journal next time(s) (even if it could change, it may be the nature s one suggested by Phil)

*Homework are about adding references in the googledoc (to build a baseline) and editor requirements (I will add some from others journals **RD->DONE**) -> Laura will do this for the paper targeted*

References are to be completed by EOSC-Life stakeholders

Meeting SP#2 09/12/2022 13:00 CEST

Laura, Helen, Jean-Marie, Phil, Romain

Outline improvement, timeline and possible agenda for december, list of participants, goal of the paper (EOSC-Life Community paper) and inclusiveness (Radical collaboration method)

Action:

- *Phil to send an email with principle of this paper and way to participate FAIRly*
- *Romain to create a Rolling notes link and zoom link for regular meetings*
- *Jean-Marie, Helen, Phil to reorganize / complete the outline*
- *All: to feed the google sheet personal info and add ideas for the first brainstorming*

Meeting SP#1 02/12/2022 16:00 CEST

Jean-Marie, Phil, Romain - first outline & googlesheet draft